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de león

Escuela de Ingenierías Industrial, Informática y Aeroespacial

MÁSTER EN INVESTIGACIÓN EN CIBERSEGURIDAD

Trabajo de Fin de Máster

AUTOMATIC CLASSIFICATION OF CYBER INCIDENTS
USING PRIVACY-PRESERVING ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE

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TÍTULO: Clasificación Automática de Ciberincidentes Usando Inteligencia Artificial que Preserva la Privacidad

TITLE: Automatic Classification of Cyber Incidents Using Privacy-Preserving Artificial Intelligence

CONVOCATORIA: September 2024

RESUMEN: A medida que los ciberincidentes aumentan en complejidad, diversidad y frecuencia, los profesionales de la ciberseguridad encuentran cada vez más difícil extraer inteligencia de amenazas e información significativa de los informes de ciberincidentes. Este problema se agrava por el número limitado de estos informes, ya que las víctimas de ciberincidentes pueden retener y/o minimizar sus informes debido a preocupaciones de reputación y privacidad.

Por lo tanto, este estudio tiene como objetivo determinar si los informes de ciberincidentes, que han sido despojados de datos personales (seudonimizados), pueden clasificarse según la Taxonomía de Ciberincidentes de INCIBE en España. Siete transformadores (SecBERT, BERT, DistilBERT, BERTweet, SecRoBERTa, ALBERT, RoBERTa) y cuatro clasificadores de aprendizaje automático tradicionales (Random Forest, Multinomial Naïve Bayes, XGBoost, Support Vector Machine, utilizando dos codificadores - Bag of Words y Term Frequency - Inverse Document Frequency), fueron entrenados para clasificar incidentes cibernéticos que fueron seudonimizados utilizando enmascaramiento de datos, tokenización de datos y sustitución de datos.

El modelo con mejor rendimiento alcanzó una puntuación F1 del 78.5% en datos no seudonimizados del conjunto de datos CECILIA-10C-900 y del 83% en el conjunto de datos que fue seudonimizado utilizando enmascaramiento de datos, D-CECILIA-10C-900-MAS. Por lo tanto, esta investigación demuestra que es posible que un único modelo de IA equilibre la mejora de la privacidad con fuertes capacidades de análisis de inteligencia de amenazas.

ABSTRACT:

As cyber incidents increase in complexity, diversity and frequency, cybersecurity practitioners find it more challenging to extract meaningful threat intelligence and insights from cyber incident reports. This problem is worsened by the limited

number of these reports; as cyber incident victims may withhold and/or downplay their reports due to reputational and privacy concerns.

Therefore, this study aims to determine whether cyber incident reports, which have been stripped of personal data (pseudonymised), can be classified according to the Spanish INCIBE Cyber Incident Taxonomy. Seven transformers (SecBERT, BERT, DistilBERT, BERTweet, SecRoBERTa, ALBERT, RoBERTa) and four traditional machine learning classifiers (Random Forest, Multinomial Naïve Bayes, XGBoost, Support Vector Machine, using two encoders - Bag of Words and Term Frequency - Inverse Document Frequency), were trained to classify cyber incidents which were pseudonymised using Data Masking, Data Tokenisation and Data Substitution.

The best-performing model attained an F1-score of 78.5% on the non-pseudonymised CECILIA-10C-900 dataset and 83% on the dataset, which was pseudonymised using Data Masking, D-CECILIA-10C-900-MAS. Therefore, this research demonstrates that it is possible for a single AI model to balance enhanced privacy with strong threat intelligence analysis capabilities.

Palabras clave: Cyber incident classification, threat intelligence, deep learning, machine learning, INCIBE Taxonomy, de-identification, cybersecurity, pseudonymisation, data masking, data substitution, data tokenisation

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Glossary of terms

Classifier: A type of machine learning model used to categorise data into predefined classes or labels.

Cyber incident: Any incident which poses a threat to the security of information systems and/or networks, regardless of the sector.

Deep Learning: A subset of machine learning that uses layers of algorithms and neurons (computing units) to analyse complex relationships and data patterns. Deep learning is different from machine learning since its layers are arranged to form an artificial neural network of three or more layers, that do not require feature engineering. This type of model also performs better when trained on larger datasets.

De-identification: Process of removing or obfuscating personal identifiers from data, such as a body of text, to preserve an individual or organisation's privacy. Compare to pseudonymisation.

INCIBE: The acronym for the Spanish National Cybersecurity Institute, or in Spanish, *Instituto Nacional de Ciberseguridad*.

Lemmatisation: The text processing technique which reduces the inflected forms of a word to its base or root form, that is, the "lemma". For example, "hugging," "hugged," and "hugs" are all reduced to the lemma "hug". This may improve the analysis and processing ability of models in various NLP tasks.

Machine Learning: The subset of Artificial Intelligence wherein customers learn from data and make predictions or decisions in a supervised or unsupervised manner.

Named Entity Recognition (NER): A sub-field of Natural Language Processing where predefined entities (such as names, organisations, and locations) can be detected in text.

Natural Language Processing (NLP): The field of Artificial Intelligence where computers understand and can generate human language through computation.

Pre-processing: The overarching term for preparing data for analysis, which can include cleaning, normalising, or otherwise transforming the data.

Privacy-preserving techniques: Methods used to protect individuals' privacy while processing and sharing data. These techniques ensure that personal and/or sensitive information remains confidential and secure.

Pseudonymisation: A privacy-preserving technique wherein personal data and other identifying data (such as quasi-identifiers) within a dataset are deleted or replaced. With the assistance of additional information, the individual to whom the personal data relates may be re-identified. In literature, pseudonymisation is often used interchangeably with de-identification, however, de-identified data is generally not intended to be re-identified, but pseudonymised data can be if needed.

Transformer: A type of deep learning model architecture that uses self-attention mechanisms to process and generate data sequences, such as text.

Vectoriser: Also referred to as an encoder, a vectoriser is a machine learning tool/algorithm that converts text data into numerical vectors, which are used as input for Machine Learning models.

1 Introduction

The twenty-first century has seen an unprecedented growth of technologies. Likewise, there has been a rise in the number of global cyber incidents; which have become increasingly varied and complex [1]. When a cyber incident occurs, it is usually documented in a cyber incident report. These reports are then analysed by researchers and cybersecurity professionals to derive threat intelligence, such as recurring attack vectors or tactics, per the MITRE ATT&CK framework¹. However, cyber incidents are reported in diverse ways. These include varied languages, reporting formats and platforms (such as social media, news outlets or formal reports to legal supervisory authorities). Together, these may make it difficult to analyse and extract meaningful insights from the cyber incidents.

Whereas Artificial Intelligence (AI) provides an alternative to the manual analysis of cyber incidents, there are palpable shortcomings. However, researchers estimate that only 3% of cyber events are accounted for in publicly-reported events databases [2]. In spite of legislation which mandates cyber incident reporting, organisations and other cyber incident victims may be reluctant to report these incidents. Reporting cyber incidents may result in litigation and investigation costs, reputational damage (for organisations and possibly their victims), and even stock price fluctuations, as was seen in the Anthem Data Breach [3]. However, the scarcity of training data available for these AI models can negatively impact the models' accuracy.

On the other hand, it is also difficult to automate the process of classifying cyber incidents since there is no globally common cyber incident taxonomy. Without a means to effectively analyse and classify these growing numbers of cyber incidents and convert them into threat intelligence, organisations may struggle to make informed decisions, potentially leading to poor resource allocation such as overspending or leaving critical assets unprotected [3]. Likewise, well-classified cyber incidents can make it easier to detect patterns and configure automated

¹ Though out of scope for this body of research, more information on the Mitre ATT&CK framework can be found at attack.mitre.org.

responses. This can be crucial in informed risk management and regulatory compliance. On a long-term basis, classification may also help with post-incident analysis which can help organisations improve their security posture over time, and even lead to proactive threat hunting as they are better able to anticipate future threats.

Recent literature has shown that deep learning and machine learning models can successfully classify cyber incidents by risk levels [4], threat actors [5], and location [6]. Furthermore, there is an emerging trend of using ensemble methods which yields promising results [7]. However, a recurrent complaint among researchers was the need for more balanced and reliable data sets [5], [8]. Additionally, there appeared to be little to no consensus on the best way to classify cyber incidents, as researchers used a plethora of incongruent taxonomies. This fragmentation underscores the need for comprehensive, standardised classification taxonomy [9]. To circumvent these problems, researchers have adopted several varied measures. Some researchers [10], have scoped their research to only examine very specific types of cyber incidents, such as social engineering attacks [10]. Others have limited the language of the cyber incidents classified, such as Sharif et al. [7], who only examined cyber incidents in Bengali. Likewise, Liu et al. [11] have used data augmentation to improve the size and quality of their dataset.

Moreover, since cyber incidents dataset in the literature were gathered from cyber threat reports or crowd-sourced through social media, the reports may contain personal data. Unfortunately, none of the studies reviewed included measures to protect the victims' privacy. Though the application of privacy-preserving techniques to text data has become a popular area of research, this research is mostly limited to the healthcare domain [12]. This domain is governed by very specific legislation and jargon, thus making it hard to generalise the results obtained there to other systems.

Therefore, this solution will satisfy a unique research gap. Seven deep learning models and four machine learning models will be trained and evaluated on their ability to classify cyber incident reports, pseudonymised using three different techniques: Data Masking, Data Tokenisation and Data Substitution (described in further detail in Section 4). The cyber incidents will be classified based on the

Spanish INCIBE Cyber Incident taxonomy (refer to Appendix 1 for this taxonomy). These incident reports, reflect all ten categories of cyber incidents from the INCIBE taxonomy. Therefore, the conclusions drawn from this study are supported by a wide variety of cyber incidents. By pseudonymising the cyber incidents used to train the model, this research also expands the current trend of using clinical datasets for researching privacy-preserving techniques. Furthermore, pseudonymisation is recognised and encouraged under European Union law (for example, under the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) Article 6(4)(e)) [13] as a means of safeguarding data [14].

Consequently, this body of research will help to preserve the privacy of cyber incident victims while helping organisations to minimise fears of reputational damage when reporting cyber incidents. This could inspire trust in the Cybersecurity sector and encourage more people to report cyber incidents, which could lead to an improvement in the quantity and quality of training data for AI models. In turn, this will improve the state of threat intelligence, and encourage collective cyber-defence efforts. Additionally, fine-tuning and training models on pseudonymised data makes the models less vulnerable to privacy attacks where adversaries attempt to extract information about models' training corpora [15]. Cybersecurity incident response teams and researchers will also derive benefits. Incident response teams will more efficiently manage and sort cyber incident reports to extract threat intelligence, since the models trained in this research demonstrate an accurate and automated way to classify cyber incidents. Researchers will also have greater ease in sharing cyber incident research across teams since they will be able to share pseudonymised cyber incidents without compromising downstream utility. In summary, this solution will build trust, enhance privacy and support effective threat intelligence extraction.

2 Project management

2.1 OBJECTIVES

The primary objective of this research is to implement a solution that balances the analysis, classification and sharing of cyber incident data with the need to protect personal data. This will be done by developing an Artificial Intelligence (AI) model that can accurately classify cyber incident reports, based on a selected cyber incident taxonomy. Then, the model will be re-evaluated on its ability to classify cyber incidents that have been pseudonymised in three different ways: Data Masking, Data Tokenisation and Data Substitution.

Given that personal data (and its quasi-identifiers) should contain little to no information about the cyber incident itself, the researcher hypothesises that AI models will perform equally when classifying non-pseudonymised datasets and when classifying pseudonymised datasets. Furthermore, recent literature [15], [16] reveals that de-identified and pseudonymised clinical data can be classified with little to no loss of data utility; therefore, it is likely that pseudonymised cyber incidents should show little to no reduction in downstream utility for classification tasks.

The primary objective of this study has been simplified into the following specific objectives:

1. Review the literature and identify the current state of the art for Machine learning classifiers which perform each of the following: Natural Language Processing, Named Entity Recognition and implementation of privacy-preserving techniques.
2. Implement and train Machine Learning and Deep Learning classifiers to classify the cyber incidents based on the INCIBE Cyber Incident Taxonomy [17]. Compare the performance of the classifiers on the CECILIA-10C-900 [18], a dataset of cyber incidents that were manually labelled based on the INCIBE Cyber Incident Taxonomy.

3. Identify and implement three privacy-preserving techniques on the CECILIA-10C-900 dataset, thereby creating three new pseudonymised datasets.
4. Evaluate and compare the performance of the Machine Learning and Deep Learning classifiers in classifying the pseudonymised cyber incidents.
5. Determine whether an AI model exists that can accurately classify both pseudonymised and non-pseudonymised cyber incidents and determine whether its performance is affected by privacy-preserving techniques.

This research will contribute to the cybersecurity field by providing a robust, privacy-preserving tool for managing the complexities of cyber incidents. This will ultimately enhance organisations' ability to defend against emerging threats, while maintaining the privacy of cyber incident victims.

Immediately following this section, is Section 2.2, which will address the planning of this project including the tasks and budget. In the subsequent section, Section 3, there will be a literature review, focusing on the current state of the art in: Natural Language Processing, Named Entity Recognition and Privacy-preserving techniques, at the time of the review. Section 4, discusses the European Union legislation which guided this project, followed by Section 5 which details the methodology of the experiment. This is followed by Sections 6 and 7, which are the results of the experiments and a discussion of these results. Finally, in Section 8, the conclusions from this research will be presented, including the limitations. This research then ends with recommendations for future work in Section 9.

2.2 PROJECT ORGANISATION

This project was executed in two phases. In the first phase, the Group for Vision and Intelligent Systems (GVIS) Research Group provided the CECILIA-10C-900 dataset and manually annotated it with eighteen categories of entities. The second phase of the project involved project planning and management, performing the literature review, manipulating the dataset, and then constructing and evaluating the models. These two phases were executed asynchronously.

This project required two types of resources available: personnel and technological. The GVIS Research Group provided one staff member to label the

CECILIA-10C-900-NER dataset, which was used in this study. I also have two supervisors who jointly allocated an estimated 40 hours to project planning, management and review. The remaining tasks were completed solely by the researcher responsible for this project. The technological resources used for this project are described in detail in Section 6.1 Development Environment.

In order to make the best use of the resources available, a project plan was designed to schedule the necessary tasks. The tasks were order according to the Machine Learning Pipeline comprised of: Data Acquisition, Data Preprocessing, Model Selection and Training, Model Evaluation and Fine-tuning.

GVIS personnel and the project supervisors exercised complete autonomy over their schedule and tools used. Therefore, this sub-section therefore focuses on the tasks assigned to this researcher. These tasks are documented in Table 2.1 and represented graphically in the Gantt Chart in Figure 2.1. It is important to note that no tasks were scheduled in Weeks 2 -3 of June 2024, to facilitate a prior scheduled engagement. All tasks were completed on-time and with the planned resources.

Project Duration: 102 days (20 May 2024 - 30 August 2024)				
Task	Sub Task	Start Date	End Date	Duration (Days)
Project Planning and Management	Define project scope and requirements.	20-May-24	03-Jun-24	14
	Develop project timeline and milestones.	20-May-24	03-Jun-24	14
Literature Review	Review of literature to determine the state of the art in similar datasets to the CECILIA-10C-900 dataset for NER.	28-Jun-24	19-Jul-24	21
	Review of literature on privacy-preserving techniques for text classification.	28-Jun-24	19-Jul-24	21
	Review of literature to verify what is the state of the art in similar datasets to the CECILIA-10C-900 dataset for NLP text classification.	28-Jun-24	19-Jul-24	21
	Literature review on text classification of cyber incidents, showing a mix of ML and DL.	28-Jun-24	19-Jul-24	21
Data Collection and Preprocessing	Collect and pseudonymise datasets of cyber incidents.	12-Jul-24	19-Jul-24	7
	Clean and preprocess the data, ensuring it's suitable for model training.	12-Jul-24	19-Jul-24	7
	Label the CECILIA-10C-900 dataset (done by the GVIS Research Team, and therefore excluded from Figure 2.1)	01-July-24	15-July-24	15
	Explore and understand the data.	12-Jul-24	19-Jul-24	7
	Pseudonymise personal data, in alignment with privacy regulations.	12-Jul-24	19-Jul-24	7
Model Selection and Development	Choose appropriate machine learning algorithms for classification.	22-Jul-24	05-Aug-24	14
	Develop and train the AI model using the pre-processed data.	22-Jul-24	05-Aug-24	14
	Test the model with a validation dataset to assess accuracy.	22-Jul-24	05-Aug-24	14

Documentation and Training	Document the AI model's development process, including code, data, and methodologies.	31-Jul-24	18-Aug-24	18
Milestone	Full draft of the TFM dissertation	18-Aug-24	18-Aug-24	1
Milestone	Supervisor's 1st revision is completed and student's corrections begin	23-Aug-24	23-Aug-24	1
Milestone	Supervisor's 2nd revision is completed and student's corrections begin	30-Aug-24	30-Aug-24	1

Table 2.1. Table showing project tasks with respective timelines (Source: Author)

Figure 2.1. Gantt chart illustrating project tasks, milestones and durations (Source: Author)

2.2.1 BUDGET

If this project were to be deployed in a business setting, it is recommended that the team include, at minimum, a Data Engineer, a Machine Learning Engineer, and a Project Manager who can work in parallel. The proposed budget for this organisation and the justification for each value is presented in Table 2.2. All values were quoted in United States Dollars for ease of comparison.

Expense	Estimated Cost / USD	Comment
Personnel Costs	45,962.00	
1 Technical Project Manager for the entire project	33,807.72	<p>The candidate is not required to have specialised knowledge of technical frameworks; a basic foundation will suffice. This is an mid-level role which would require the individual to oversee for 102 days the project lifecycle, define project scope, requirements, timeline and milestones, and support the documentation of the AI model’s development process, including code, data, and methodologies.</p> <p>A Senior Technical Project Manager with 3 to 5 years of experience earns \$98,000 yearly (\$8,166.67 monthly) working at a company with a headcount of 501-1000 employees and a Technical Project Manager with 3 to 5 years of experience earns \$135,000 per year (\$11,250 monthly) working at a company with 51-200 employees². Based on these figures, the selected Technical Project Manager would receive a median compensation of \$9,708.33 monthly which would be equivalent to \$33,807.72 for working 102 days.</p>
2 Data Engineers for 7 days	2384.62	<p>Multiple similarities were noted between the job description of Apex Fintech Solutions’ Data Engineer vacancy notice³ and the role requirements for this project. For instance, both are seeking a candidate who has 1 to 3 years of experience with a background in Python, data engineering and analysis, cloud data technologies, and the ability and willingness to learn new things (languages, tools, frameworks) quickly. Apex is also an</p>

² Salary estimate obtained from <https://builtin.com/salaries/project-mgmt/technical-project-manager>

³ See <https://builtin.com/job/data-engineer/2803916>

		<p>SME with 750 employees. According to Glassdoor⁴, the estimated total pay range for a Data Engineer at Apex Fintech Solutions is \$95K-\$132K per year (\$1,826.92 to 2,538.46 per week), which includes base salary and additional pay.</p> <p>The selected Data Engineer will be paid a total of \$1,192.31 for the 7 days, which is \$634.61 less than the minimum rate set by Apex. The setting of this price is deliberate because the selected Data Engineer’s scope of responsibilities would be narrower than those outlined in Apex’s job description. However, it is noted that the datasets of cyber incidents would need to be acquired, pre-processed and pseudonymised within 7 days. This is predicted to be a time-intensive task considering for instance, that CECILIA-10C-900 contains 923 records with an average text length (characters) of 821.74, D-CECILIA-10C-900 contains 880 records with an average text length (characters) of 742.10, and D-CECILIA-6C-900 contains 852 records with average text length (characters) of 738.99.</p> <p>Therefore, two Data Engineers will be recruited to manipulate the datasets to ensure adherence to the stipulated 7-day period and each would receive a total of \$1,192.31 (which is \$238.46 per day). It is assumed that a data engineer at the junior level would not yet be sufficiently skilled to efficiently and singlehandedly manipulate the data within a week.</p>
<p>1 Machine Learning Engineer for 21 days</p>	<p>5653.86</p>	<p>US-based smaller companies and startups typically pay AI Engineers between \$80,000 to \$130,000 yearly which is equivalent to \$1,538.46 to \$2500.00 weekly⁵. AI Engineers with 2 to 4 years of experience make an average of \$106,894 yearly which is equivalent to</p>

⁴ (https://www.glassdoor.com/Salary/Apex-Fintech-Solutions-Data-Engineer-Salaries-E599382_D_KO23,36.htm)

⁵ Data extracted from <https://www.geeksforgeeks.org/how-much-do-ai-engineers-make-salary-guide-2024/>

		<p>\$2,055.65 weekly. According to salary reports on Glassdoor, both Artificial Learning and Machine Learning engineers are paid similarly.</p> <p>The selected Machine Learning Engineer will be paid \$1884.62 per week for a total of 3 weeks. This figure is deliberately \$346.16 greater than the minimum rate and \$615.38 less than the maximum rate offered by startups and smaller companies. The volume and nature of work require a Machine Learning Engineer with 1 to 2 years of experience who can work remotely and is eager to learn and grow in the industry. This estimated cost prioritises the importance of keeping operational costs low in the early stages of project execution.</p>
<p>Cybersecurity Consultant to label dataset for 40 hours.</p>	<p>2080</p>	<p>The average base salary estimate of \$51.75 per hour is based on 63 salaries submitted anonymously to Indeed by cybersecurity consultant employees and users collected from past and present job posts on Indeed in the past 36 months. The figure was rounded up to \$52 which the selected candidate would receive each hour for 40 hours⁶.</p>
<p>Legal Consultant for 4-5 hours</p>	<p>136.25</p>	<p>There is limited data available on the salary range for lawyers with expertise in GDPR and other legal compliance. However, Data Privacy Lawyers make an average of \$48.38 hourly (\$100,626 a year)⁷. The lowest and highest annual salaries recorded by ZipRecruiter were \$47,000 and \$138,000, respectively.</p>

⁶ Please see related link with salary summary: <https://www.indeed.com/career/cybersecurity-consultant/salaries>

⁷ Data extracted from <https://www.ziprecruiter.com/Salaries/Data-Privacy-Lawyer-Salary>

		The lawyer would provide his/her services on a contractual basis. The salary offering would be \$26.45 per hour for five hours. It is not financially or operationally feasible or necessary to retain the lawyer on a full-time basis.
Quality Assurance Tester for 2 weeks	1900	Junior Quality Assurance Testers ⁸ earn an average of \$1053 per week. The lowest and highest weekly salaries recorded by Indeed were \$859 and \$1290, respectively. The selected candidate will receive a salary of \$950 per week for 2 weeks.
Hardware and Infrastructure		
	40	
Firestore Database	0	Firestore offers a free quota of up to 1 GB of stored data which is applied daily and resets around midnight Pacific time ⁹ .
Firebase Hosting (to host and deploy services)	0	There are two pricing options - the (complimentary) Spark Plan and the (premium) Blaze Plan. The former offers custom model deployment with the possibility to upgrade to the latter in the future ¹⁰ .
Google Collab Subscription	40	The least expensive package is “Pay As You Go” which allows you to purchase more compute units as you need them. To start, one can purchase 100 compute units for \$9.99 per month or 500 compute units for \$49.99 ¹¹ .

⁸ Data extracted from <https://www.indeed.com/career/quality-assurance-tester/salaries>

⁹ Based on <https://cloud.google.com/firestore/pricing>

¹⁰ Refer to <https://firebase.google.com/pricing>

¹¹ Based on <https://colab.research.google.com/signup>.

NVIDIA® T4 GPU	0	The NVIDIA® T4 GPU accelerates diverse cloud workloads, including high-performance computing, deep learning training and inference, machine learning, data analytics, and graphics ¹² . This is included with the Google Colab premium package.
Software Tools		
Deep Learning Frameworks and ML Tools	0	This project will utilise open-source tools (like <i>HuggingFace</i> Library and <i>TensorFlow</i>) to minimise operational costs
Project Management Tool: Clickup	0	Clickup, a popular customisable comprehensive project management software, has a free forever package which offers 100MB storage, unlimited tasks, unlimited free plan members, two-factor authentication, collaborative docs, real-time chat, kanban boards, sprint management, among other features ¹³ .
Data Acquisition		
Cyber Incident Datasets	0	Peers in the GVIS Research GroupLab (https://gvis.unileon.es/) provided the datasets upon which this research is based. Therefore, there is no associated cost.

¹² Sources: <https://www.nvidia.com/en-us/data-center/tesla-t4/> and <https://cloud.google.com/compute/gpus-pricing>

¹³ Source: <https://clickup.com/pricing>

Outreach and Collaboration	81,683	
Marketing and Public Relations	81,683	The average salary for a Services Marketing role is \$81,683 per year ¹⁴ . Considering that the project is relatively new to the market and the team has not developed a reputation and network, there may be little to no room for negotiation of compensation. Therefore, the \$81,683 will be used as an estimate for the cost of services to be rendered.
Miscellaneous and Contingency Fund	18,903	10-15% of the total budget
Total Estimated Budget	146,837.75	

Table 2.2. Table showing proposed project budget (Source: Author)

¹⁴ According to https://www.glassdoor.com/Salaries/marketing-services-salary-SRCH_K00,18.htm

3 State of the art

This section begins with a review of the state of the art for Named Entity Recognition models, which is up to date as of the time of this review. This review prioritises studies that were done using similar datasets to the ones used during this study, such as CECILIA-10C-900. Subsequently, this section examines advancements from the last two years in the field of Natural Language Processing when applied to text classification of Cybersecurity incidents. These are separated into those cyber incidents that were user-generated like help desk tickets or some social media posts, and those which were non-user generated, such as threat intelligence reports. The section then concludes with a review of studies which implemented privacy-enhancing techniques used on text datasets, emphasising those which assessed the downstream utility of the data.

Accuracy, F1-score, precision and recall are the main metrics used to evaluate model performance in this review. Accuracy is an overall measure of correct predictions and the F1-score represents the harmonic mean of precision and recall. Unlike the F1-score, accuracy is best suited for balanced datasets. Precision is the balance of correctly-identified positive instances, out of all positive predictions. Meanwhile, recall (or sensitivity) is a model's ability to correctly predict the positive class. In Section 6.2: Metrics, the equations for these metrics, and their relevance to this research problem are discussed in greater detail.

3.1 NAMED ENTITY RECOGNITION

Named Entity Recognition (NER) is a subfield of Artificial Intelligence that takes unstructured text and identifies entities such as location, person name, and organisation, as well as temporal and quantitative expressions [19]. In this subsection, the current state of the art for NER in Machine Learning and Deep Learning will be examined, focusing on flat, nested (or overlapped), and discontinuous cases of NER. Across the literature, these types of NER have been processed separately, though there is a trend towards concurrently solving all types using a single model [20]. This subsection then concludes with a review of the current, state-of-the-art methods using NER in cyber incident-related datasets. The studies reviewed in the section are summarised in Table 3.1.

3.1.1 FLAT CASE NER

This is where entities exist in a text without a hierarchical or overlapping structure. In the following Flat Case NER example, ‘Erin Harrison visited the Oakland Zoo yesterday’, ‘Erin Harrison’ is the person entity and ‘Oakland Zoo’ is the location entity [21]. The literature shows that NER models generally yield better results when performing on Flat Case NER datasets.

Overall, the best performance in Flat Case NER is the W^2 NER model [22], with a 0.9610 F1 score in the Mandarin-language MSRA-NER dataset [23]. The W^2 NER model is a unified NER model, therefore it can process the three types of NER. It functions by parsing the data into word pairs and using a co-predictor to predict the word relations; with a BERT-Bi-LSTM backbone. This is beneficial because the relationship between the words can then be used to determine the entity label. This model was also assessed on an English Flat NER dataset, CoNLL2003 [24]. This dataset contains Reuters news articles annotated with entities of the following categories: location, person, organisation and miscellaneous. On this dataset, the W^2 NER model achieved an F1-score of 0.9307, whereas the state-of-the-art was the T^2 -NER model [20] which achieved a 0.9413 F1-score. This model extracts entity spans and performs the entity classification on these entity span pairs. Similar to W^2 NER, this model also performs on the three types of NER, since it uses multi-task learning which connects the entity spans to the entity classification. Unfortunately, this approach negatively affects the performance speed. Notably, Li et al. [25] achieved the highest recall on that dataset (0.9461) in 2020, and this has remained the state of the art for recall on that dataset, at the point when this review was done; surpassing W^2 NER’s achieved recall of 0.934.

Notwithstanding, Rucker and Akbik [26] discovered that the CoNLL2003 corpus has multiple annotation errors, instances of incompleteness, and overall inconsistencies, which could negatively affect the models’ performance. They subsequently introduced CleanCoNLL, which they show can help state-of-the-art models improve their performance, thus indicating that the models discussed prior have the potential to score even higher.

3.1.2 NESTED NER

This is where entities are present in a text with a hierarchical or overlapping structure. Wang et al. [21] provide the following example, ‘ A spokesman for the Oakland Zoo said...’,

where the location, Oakland, is contained or nested within the location entity, Oakland Zoo. NER models that perform using nested NER tasks, can also recognise flat NER.

Across the literature, when nested NER models are tested on the ACE 2004 dataset [27], they generally show stronger F1 score performance than other datasets. The ACE 2004 dataset is composed of broadcast news and cell records of varying lengths, with seven entity tags: facility, geo-political entity, location, organisation, person, vehicle and weapon.

The T2-NER model [20], again holds the state of the art for both F1-score (0.894) and precision (0.9088) in this task, as at the point of this review. However, the Bi-DCAN model [28] holds the state of the art for recall with 0.8868, performing slightly better than the DiffusionNER [29] model's 0.8866 recall. This was a difference of 0.0002 and therefore could be due to rounding differences. This Bi-DCAN model introduces a new span-level semantic relation model, which does not require it to decode entity spans independently. It also requires less than half of the processing time (calculated as the number of epochs required for the model to achieve its maximum F1-score) and 20 million fewer parameters than DiffusionNER. This was due to DiffusionNER being a latent generative model that used the boundary diffusion technique to produce random characteristic entity generation. Since that model performed 'denoising' before identifying the entities, its performance was negatively impacted.

The PIQN model [30] also achieved similar performance to the state-of-the-art model, achieving a 0.8814 F1-score on the same dataset. Unlike the other two models, PIQN demonstrates enhanced processing capabilities since it uses a parallel instance query network which allows it to perform concurrent entity recognition tasks. In contrast, in a case study, the model lacked an understanding of special phrases (such as incorrectly concluding that since Yahoo! is an organisation, then Yahoo! Communications Services is an organisation as well) and was 'insensitive to morphological variation'.

3.1.3 DISCONTINUOUS NER

Discontinuous NER is the most complex of the three NER tasks, with multiple nested overlaps occurring with various degrees of complexity. An example of discontinuous NER is seen in Figure 3.1. In the literature, models performed best on the ShARe13 dataset [31], [32], which has a biomedical corpus domain including discharge summaries and medical reports. Hu et al. [33] used a Span-based NER model to achieve an F1 score of 0.838 which

was the state of the art at the time of this review. Notably, this model’s performance was hindered by a poor understanding of prepositions, since prepositions in a phrase can change the entity type. Subsequently, Mao et al. [34] were able to use ClinicalBERT to achieve a 0.8260 F1-score; which did not exhibit the same limitations regarding prepositions. This is possibly due to its position-aware bi-affine predictor, which uses the relative position information to classify the entities. However, like DiffusionNER [29], the model had low efficiency, contributing to the lower than the state-of-the-art results obtained in nested and flat NER [35].

Figure 3.1. Examples of sentences with discontinuous entities. Sentence (a), shows the overlap of a discontinuous entity (“fingers hurt”) with continuous entities. Sentence (b) shows that two discontinuous entities can overlap (“Elevated left sided filling pressures” and “Elevated right sided filling pressures”). Sentence (c) demonstrates four overlapping discontinuous entities and (d) shows where a single phrase, ‘lung’ can be shared by two discontinuous entities in “consolidation lung” and “lung contusion”. (Source: Mao et al. [34])

3.1.4 USING NER ON CYBER INCIDENT DATASETS

The literature reveals a trend of training Named Entity Recognition (NER) on datasets that include domains such as cyber incidents, instead of the traditionally popular clinical and news-related datasets. However, due to the paucity of datasets available for cyber incidents, it is challenging to find studies which have been evaluated on the same dataset. This makes performing a balanced comparison difficult. Nonetheless, this section will

compare the results of two recent studies, which were evaluated on similar datasets and showed state-of-the-art results.

Ahmed et al. [36] trained a RoBERTa-BiGRU-CRF model to identify entities such as algorithms, malware, corporations and Advanced Persistent Threat (APT) groups. The model was also able to identify the relationships between entities, for example, 'Ransomware is a type of malware'. This model achieved a 0.832 F1-score, with a precision of 0.894, when assessed on an unnamed Cyber Threat Intelligence (CTI) dataset. This dataset contained manually annotated reports of APT and ransomware attacks. However, the small scope of the study raises questions about its scalability, especially since the model was assessed on a small dataset.

On the other hand, Wang et al. [37] gathered 8,872 instances of threat intelligence from a variety of sources such as security blogs and forum posts, which contained over 28,000 entities. A pre-trained BERT model was used to identify the identity or location of an attacker or his/her intermediary. To accomplish this, the researchers considered each sentence to be a sentence tree graph. Subsequently, they extracted the entities from these graphs using graph attention networks which were enriched with cybersecurity knowledge. This approach yielded a 0.9016 F1-score. The model also had a 0.9296 precision score indicating few false positive predictions. A limitation of this approach is that without including specific solutions and tools (software, hardware, networks, etc) as an entity, then the real-life applicability of this solution could be limited since threat intelligence is often parsed by tool or solution.

Type of NER	Authors	Year	Model	F1-score	Recall	Precision	Dataset	Limitations
Flat	Huang et al.	2023	T2-NER	0.9413	0.9448	0.9378	CoNLL2003	Slower PERFORMANCE than the W2NER
	Li et al.	2020	BERT-MRC	0.9304	0.9461	0.9233		Performs poorly on unseen entity labels (zero-shot evaluation).
	Shen et al.	2023	DiffusionNER	0.9278	0.9256	0.9299		Does not have the capability to process datasets with the Discontinued NER
	X Li et al. ¹⁵	2022	W2NER	0.9307	0.9344	0.9271		CoNLL2003 dataset is believed to have multiple annotation errors, incompleteness and inconsistencies.
	Y Shen et al.	2022	PIQN	0.9287	0.9246	0.9329		Demonstrated a lack of understanding of special phrases (Yahoo! Is the organisation and it considers Yahoo! Communications services as an organisation too), and insensitivity to morphological variation (e.g. Venezuelan vs Venezuela)

¹⁵ In this summary table, there are three separate studies written by Li et al and two studies written by Shen et al. In order to easily differentiate between these studies, the first-name initial of the first author is included in this table.

Type of NER	Authors	Year	Model	F1-score	Recall	Precision	Dataset	Limitations
Nested	Huang et al.	2023	T2-NER	0.894	0.8797	0.9088	ACE2004	Slower PERFORMANCE than the W2NER
	Shen et al.	2023	DiffusionNER	0.8839	0.8866	0.8811		The 'denoising' slows its performance
	X Li et al.	2022	W2NER	0.8752	0.8641	0.8733		Did not provide a breakdown of the model's performance by entity type, only an average, thus it is possible that the model may perform poorly on minority-class entities.
	Y Shen et al.	2022	PIQN	0.8814	0.8781	0.8848		Same as in the prior section, Flat NER.
	Y. Li et al.	2024	Bi-DCAN	0.8828	0.8868	0.8802		Limited scope, can only perform on nested and flat NER tasks.
Discontinuous	Hu et al.	2023	EnTDA	0.833	-	-	ShARe13	Difficulty in generalisation
	Huang et al.	2023	T2-NER	0.838	0.8048	0.8741		Difficulties in assimilating prepositions, negatively affects its entity classification abilities.
	Mao et al.	2024	ClinicalBERT	0.826	0.7971	0.8597		Decoding ambiguity hampers performance and causes low efficiency
	X Li et al.	2022	W2NER	0.8252	0.7968	0.8557		There was no breakdown of the model's performance by entity type. With only an average, the model's performance in minority classes is unknown.

Type of NER	Authors	Year	Model	F1-score	Recall	Precision	Dataset	Limitations
Mixed (Cyber incident datasets)	Ahmed et al.	2024	RoBERTa-BiGRU-CRF	0.832	0.778	0.894	Unnamed CTI corpus of 100 CTI articles about APT and ransomware attacks.	The dataset is narrowly scoped, as it only includes APT and ransomware attacks; this may affect the study's real-life utility.
	Wang et al.	2024	KnowCTI	0.9016	0.8752	0.9296	Threat data from security blogs, forum posts, etc with 28,348 entities across 8,872 instances.	The model does not consider the names of hardware, software or tools as entities; therefore, the solution could have limited real-life utility.

Table 3.1. Table summarising the best performing models in the flat, nested, discontinuous and cyber incident (mixed) NER tasks. (Source: Author)

3.2 USING NATURAL LANGUAGE PROCESSING IN THE CLASSIFICATION OF CYBER INCIDENT REPORTS

Being able to quickly analyse cybersecurity incidents to provide a prompt and effective response is a global priority, especially for security response centres, such as CSIRTs (Computer Security Incident Response Teams). In the literature, both machine and deep learning models have shown promise in classifying cybersecurity incident reports at different levels of granularity. In these studies, there are generally two types of cyber incident reports: user-generated and threat intelligence reports. An example of the first could be an employee reporting unauthorised access through a company's help desk ticket system, while threat intelligence reports are made by security companies and sometimes news agencies. In this section of the literature review, both report types will be examined, with an emphasis placed on bodies of work which incorporate deep learning from 2022 to the present. The studies reviewed in this section are summarised in Table 3.2.

3.2.1 CLASSIFYING USER-GENERATED CYBER INCIDENT REPORTS

Meher et al. [38] demonstrated that with a BERT classifier, they could separate non-security bugs from security-related bugs on a dataset of 1.36 million bug reports from a Bugzilla Platform. These bugs came from eight types of open-source projects, one of which was security-related. They pre-processed bug summaries through tokenisation, stop-word removal, and lemmatisation; and then used an attention-based classification technique with BERT. The performance of BERT was compared against CodeBERT, DistilBERT and a 'vanilla Transformers-based classifier'. Then, it was again compared to Logistic Regression (LR), Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM), Attention mechanisms, and Attention with Latent Dirichlet Allocation. BERT consistently achieved the highest accuracy, with its best F1 score being 0.8944. However, despite the high F1 score, the classification could benefit from a more granular taxonomy.

On the other hand, Aun et al. [10] were able to classify social media posts into the following cyber incident categories of social engineering attacks: phishing, pretexting, scareware, clickbait, and quid pro quo from their custom dataset of annotated Facebook posts. Then, they trained a Recurrent Neural Network - Long Short-Term Memory (RNN-LSTM) model, which achieved a recall of 0.84 and a precision of 0.81. This model outperformed the following classifiers: K-Nearest Neighbours (KNN), Decision Tree (DT) using J48

implementation, Deep Belief Network (DBN), Principal Component Analysis (PCA), Random Forest (RF), and Multilayer Perceptron (MLP). However, the authors did not compare the models using popular metrics such as accuracy or F1-score. Therefore, it is difficult to benchmark the models' results against other studies.

Subsequently, Sharif et al. [7] proposed an ensemble architecture for classifying 'aggressive texts' in Bengali, using a custom manually annotated dataset (M-BAD) from various social media sources. This is an example of multilabel classification, where each text is first binarily classified as aggressive/non-aggressive. Then aggressive posts are categorised by target, namely religion, politics, verbal (that is, using curse words or other obscenity), gender and race. They compared machine learning (LR, RF, Naïve Bayes (NB), SVM) models that used Bag of Word encoding with deep learning (BiGRU using FastText embeddings), and transformer models (m-BERT, Indic-BERT, Bangla-BERT). Bangla-BERT achieved the best performance with a weighted F1-score of 0.83. This body of work explores an underdeveloped field, because of the language and the taxonomy used. However, unlike Aun et al. [10], the researchers believed that the performance of their model was hindered by implicit or sarcastic aggression, which the model found challenging to detect. Additionally, the dataset was poorly balanced, with the race category having 1,711 instances in the training set, compared to 30,748 in the religion category.

Like Sharif et al., Lughbi et al. [4] also extensively utilised BERT transformers in their research. However, Lughbi et al. developed a system to classify tweets about cyber incidents into risk levels: 'high-risk news', 'normal news', and 'non-news'. They used Count Vectorisers and TF-IDF with bigram to evaluate various machine learning algorithms (LR, Multinomial Naïve Bayes (MNB), DT, KNN, SVM) and deep learning models (DistilBERT, DeBERTa, BERT, RoBERTa). Unlike the other papers examined up to this point in this review, the Machine Learning classifier, Logistic Regression, was their best-performing model and achieved an F1-score of 0.876. Though this model allows real-time cyber incident detection, three volunteers manually labelled the tweets, which can introduce human error and bias. This could affect the accuracy and reliability of the dataset and the classification model.

Wahba et al. [39] compared the performance of SVM with TF-IDF vectorised text and four pre-trained language models (BERT, DistilBERT, RoBERTa, XLM) on datasets like BBC News [40], 20News Group [41], Customer Complaints [42] and a private, domain-specific dataset of IT Support Tickets. For this review, the emphasis is placed on the IT Support Tickets,

which were to be classified into categories such as 'Project Office' and 'Security and Identity'. They found that SVM was the most successful, achieving an F1-score of 0.79 on the imbalanced IT domain dataset. This imbalance means that all classes in the dataset are not represented equally. Instead, some classes may have more samples than others, which may affect the model's training and introduce bias into the model. Furthermore, like with Meher et al. [38], the taxonomy could benefit from greater granularity. Additionally, the dataset contains other non-cyber incident tickets.

Of note, Liu et al. [43] introduced Ticket-BERT, demonstrating that a deep learning transformer model which performed comparably to the machine learning model implemented in the last paper. The model was fine-tuned on Microsoft Kusto tickets from June 2020 to June 2022 and then classified by categories such as CloudAlerts. They compared it against traditional models (NB, LR) and the LS-model which is a neural network model native to Microsoft's Language Studio. Ticket-BERT achieved an accuracy of 0.9862, precision of 0.9793, and recall of 0.9824. The study noted limitations in generalising across Microsoft's systems and that the dataset included other non-cyber incident tickets.

Finally, Bhowmik et al. [44] used three 'almost balanced' datasets (fake news [45], spam emails from the SpamAssassin dataset[46], and cyber-harassment from Twitter [47]) to evaluate six deep learning models (ANN, Simple RNN, GRU, LSTM, BiLSTM, CNN) and a hybrid CNN-LSTM model. The datasets were processed using a customised word embedding layer, with one hot representation and zero padding. One hot representation differentiates between words but does not provide semantic information about the relationship between words to the models. With zero padding, the models are more efficient since it is processing data in uniform batches, but this technique may introduce noise into the model. By customising these two techniques the models reported the following results: accuracy of 0.9955 for fake news (CNN), 0.9757 for spam (CNN-LSTM), and 0.9300 for cyber-harassment (CNN). The Twitter dataset's imbalance was noted as a limitation.

3.2.2 CLASSIFYING THREAT INTELLIGENCE AND NON - USER GENERATED CYBER INCIDENT REPORTS

This section of the report examines the classification of threat intelligence and cybersecurity incident reports that are non-user generated.

Onyekpeze et al. [48] obtained the best performance by using data from Nigeria's Cyber Threat Intelligence platform, spanning from 2019 to 2021. From this dataset, they extracted features such as IP addresses, ISP names, activity dates, countries, and infection types and labelled them into categories such as botnet and spam. The researchers then compared the performance of the seven classifiers, Logistic Regression, Support Vector Machine (SVM), Decision Tree (DT-CART), K-Nearest Neighbour (KNN), Naïve Bayes (NB), and Random Forest (RF) algorithms, when implemented with the KModes Clustering Algorithm, to group the data that have a similar feature. The DT, KNN and RF algorithms all achieved identical accuracy of 0.99, precision of 1.00, and recall of 0.99. Therefore, this body of work shows that machine learning algorithms are a viable option for classifying cyber threat intelligence. However, this body of research has a limited scope, as it only classified cyber threats that were present in Nigeria.

In comparison, Mumtaz et al. [6] classified Significant Cyber Incidents (SCI) documented by the Center for Strategic and International Studies. These reports spanned almost two decades and included six continents. The cyber incidents were also annotated with categories such as SQL injection, Distributed Denial of Service, Espionage, Man-in-the-Middle, etc. Subsequently, researchers used Bag of Words (BoW) to encode the unigram and bigram representations of the cyber incidents, which were then used to train and evaluate the NB, SVM, LR and RF machine learning algorithms. Given a cyber incident and its type, the classifiers predicted the continent where the cyber incident occurred. This study reported an average accuracy of 0.988 for pre-pandemic data and 0.972 for post-pandemic data for the SVM classifier. The imbalanced dataset was evaluated using accuracy. Since this metric does not appropriately account for dataset imbalance, for this literature review, the average F1-score was re-calculated. This resulted in an F1-score of 0.7567 for pre-pandemic data and 0.7633 for post-pandemic data. This reduction is due to the dataset's imbalance, such that minority classes such as Africa were incorrectly classified.

J. Liu et al. [11] classified 113,543 actionable cyber threat intelligence (CTI), such as IP addresses and hashes from cybersecurity reports into campaign stages, using a model called TriCTI. Campaign stages are also known as the stages of an attack or the Cyber Kill Chain, for example, delivery, exploitation, and installation [49]. However, the researchers also added two categories to the taxonomy: malicious and benign. The classification task was performed using BERT for pre-training trigger vectors, followed by a Trigger Enhanced Neural Network. This approach achieved an accuracy of 0.8699 and an F1-score of 0.8702. Notably, to address the shortage of training data which limited other studies [6], [48], the authors implemented data augmentation. Nevertheless, the model still performed poorly when there were complex sentences which contained multiple campaign stages.

Domschot et al. [50] aimed to improve the automated labelling of malware behaviours in threat reports from the rcATT repository using MITRE ATT&CK tactics. This study is different from the others since each report in the dataset can be classified using multiple labels, where each label is independent of the other. The classification was performed using the Logistic Regression, Least Squares Support Vector Machine (L. SVM) and Bidirectional Long Short Term Memory classifiers, each with GloVe embeddings. The L. SVM that used the mutual information technique for feature selection outperformed the other methods, achieving a precision of 0.698, a recall of 0.574, and an F0.5-score of 0.654. With an F0.5-score, the precision of the model is prioritised over the recall. This is in contrast to the F1-score that is the harmonic mean of the two values. The BiLSTM model with the GloVe embedding layer model that was trained on Information Security terms, exceeded the recall score, obtaining 0.698, though it had an F0.5-score of 0.433. The authors cited the lack of labelled threat report datasets as a limitation in this study, which affected their ability to effectively train their models.

Meanwhile, Irshad and Siddiqui [5] used a customised encoding, attack2vec, to classify cyber-attacks by their actors based on the attack patterns extracted from the threat intelligence reports. They extracted features such as Cyber Threat Actor, TTP (a high-level IOC), Malware, Tools, Target Country, and Organization. The Random Forest model with attack2vec encoding achieved an accuracy of 0.9600, precision of 0.9660, recall of 0.9558, and F1-score of 0.9575. The Random Forest model has also been the best performing model in other classification tasks reviewed in this section [48]. Nonetheless, the main challenge was the need for more available benchmark datasets, especially balanced ones.

Alternatively, Chafla and López [8] performed binary classification. They crawled The Hacker News¹⁶ to create a cyber-industrial cyber incident report dataset. They then grouped the reports into two categories: Internet of Things and Critical Infrastructure. Again, the Random Forest classifier performed the best. The Random Forest with TF-IDF encoding achieved an accuracy of 0.712, precision of 0.7172, recall of 0.712, and an F1-score of 0.7081. However, the neural network's performance was limited by the dataset's small size and representativeness.

Yosifova et al. [51] classified over twenty years of cyber incidents and vulnerabilities to classes from the Computer Security Incidents Response Taxonomy using a compositional Machine Learning algorithm. They first evaluated the performance of the Logistic Regression, Random Forest and Gradient Boosting algorithms as a baseline, then compared it to their ensemble classifier. The researchers found that though the Gradient Boosting algorithm achieved a mean accuracy of 0.903, their ensemble model achieved the highest accuracy of 0.938. The dataset that the models were evaluated on was small, which may affect the models' future ability to generalise.

Finally, Delgado et al. [18] scraped cyber incidents from five sources and created a new dataset, CECILIA-10C-900 which contained cyber incidents labelled according to the INCIBE Cyber Incident Taxonomy. Each cyber incident was assigned one label, comprising a category and its dependent sub-category. The Machine Learning classifier, MPNet performed the strongest with a weighted F1-score of 0.8273. The researchers then repeated the experiment. They reduced the imbalance of the dataset by combining the minority classes into one heading. Consequently, the models' overall performance improved with RoBERTa narrowly becoming the top performer, showing an F1-score of 0.8273. Nevertheless, the CECILIA-10C-900 dataset was manually labelled which may introduce human errors and bias into the dataset. This was seen when duplicated records in the dataset were labelled dissimilarly, thus introducing noise into the dataset. Furthermore, it is possible that a cyber incident could belong to more than one category concurrently, however, the study did not include multi-label classification.

¹⁶ The Hacker News (thehackernews.com) is an independent outlet, specialising in publishing cybersecurity news. THN claims to be the most followed business to business cybersecurity news outlet on all major social media platforms.

Authors	Publication Year	Description	DL or ML?	Results: F1-score	Limitations	Best Performing Classifier
Meher et al.	2024	Classified Bug Reports of open-source projects from Bugzilla Platform into eight classes, with one class dedicated to security issues such as unauthorised access.	DL	0.8944	The taxonomy used lacked granularity.	BERT
Aun et al.	2023	Classified social media posts into categories of social engineering attacks, including phishing, pretexting, scareware, clickbait, and quid pro quo.	DL/ML	- (P: 0.84; R: 0.81)	The study did not compare the models using popular metrics like accuracy or F1-score.	RNN LSTM
Sharif et al.	2022	Multi-label classification of aggressive texts in Bengali social media posts, focusing on categories such as religion, politics, verbal abuse, gender, and race.	DL/ML	0.83	The dataset was severely imbalanced. Additionally, the model experienced difficulty detecting implicit/sarcastic aggression.	Bangla-BERT
Lughbi et al.	2024	Classified tweets about cyber incidents into risk levels (high-risk news, normal news, non-news).	DL/ML	0.876	Potential human error in manual labelling could affect accuracy and reliability.	Logistic Regression

Wahba et al.	2023	Compared SVM with TF-IDF vectorised text and four pre-trained language models on IT Support Tickets and other datasets.	DL/ML	0.79	The IT domain dataset was severely imbalanced, and the taxonomy could benefit from greater granularity.	Linear SVM
Liu et al.	2023	Created TicketBERT, fine-tuned on Microsoft Kusto tickets from June 2020 to June 2022 and then classified by categories such as CloudAlerts.	DL	(Accuracy) 0.9862	There may be challenges in generalising the model. Furthermore, the dataset was noisy since it included other non-cyber incident tickets.	BERT
Bhowmik et al.	2024	Evaluated six deep learning models on datasets for fake news, spam emails, and cyber-harassment from Twitter.	DL	Fake news (0.99); Spam emails (0.9757); Cyber-harassment (0.93)	The Twitter dataset was severely imbalanced, which negatively impacted the models' performance on minority classes.	CNN and CNN-LSTM
Onyekpeze et al.	2021	Used data from Nigeria's Cyber Threat Intelligence platform, and extracted features from 2019-2021 to classify cyber incidents into classes like botnet and spam.	ML	0.99	Only data from Nigeria was used, therefore, the model's ability to generalise has not been proven.	Random Forest, Decision Tree, KNN (tied)

Mumtaz et al.	2023	Classified Significant Cyber Incidents (SCI) from six continents over two decades into categories like SQL injection, DDoS, etc.	ML	A: 0.99 (pre-pandemic / 0.96 post-pandemic)	Imbalance in the dataset affected performance, especially for underrepresented continents like Africa. The evaluation metric used (accuracy) was unsuitable for the imbalanced dataset.	SVM
J. Liu et al.	2022	Classified actionable cyber threat intelligence (CTI) into campaign stages using the TriCTI model with BERT for pre-training trigger vectors.	DL	0.8702	The model performs poorly on complex sentences that contain multiple campaign stages.	BERT with Trigger Enhanced Neural Network
Domschot et al.	2024	Improved automated labelling of malware behaviours in threat reports using MITRE ATT&CK tactics with multi-label classification.	DL/ML	(F0.5-score) 0.654	There was insufficient data available to optimise the training of the model.	L. SVM, with mutual information technique
Irshad and Basit Siddiqui	2023	Classified cyber actors based on their attack patterns documented in threat intelligence reports.	ML	0.9575	There was a lack of available balanced, benchmark datasets.	RF
Chafla and Lopez	2023	Performed binary classification on cyber-physical cyber incident reports.	ML	0.7081	The small size of the dataset limited the	RF with TF-IDF

					training data available for the models.	
Yosifova et al.	2022	Performed multi-label classification on cyber incidents and vulnerabilities.	ML	0.938	The dataset that the models were evaluated on was small, and this may affect the models' future ability to generalise.	Ensemble method
Delgado et al.	2024	Created a labelled cyber incident dataset containing cyber incidents from all categories in the INCIBE Taxonomy (CECILIA-10C-900). Then, the incidents were classified by category.	ML/DL	(weighted F1-score) 0.8273	The dataset contained duplicated cyber incidents, that were sometimes classified in dissimilar ways which created noisy training data for the model. Also, the study did not perform multi-label classification.	MPNet

Table 3.2. Table summarising the performance of models used to classify cyber incident reports, where the blue background represents user-generated incident reports (Source: Author)

3.3 PRIVACY-PRESERVING TECHNIQUES

Recent literature on privacy-preserving techniques using machine learning models highlights three main approaches: anonymisation, de-identification, and differential privacy. This review explores the literature available for each of these techniques, emphasising the advancements between 2022 and 2024 and highlighting the commonalities and distinctions between these approaches.

Firstly, it is important to note that the techniques used for de-identification, pseudonymisation and anonymisation are almost identical. Therefore, in the literature, these terms are sometimes used interchangeably. This is controversial since there is a crucial difference between the three terms. The anonymised data subjects should never be re-identified; with de-identification and pseudonymisation, the data subjects can be re-identified. The European Union Agency for Cybersecurity (ENISA) [52] considers pseudonymisation to be a type of deidentification. However, with pseudonymisation, it is understood that there may be future reidentification of data subjects, whereas, with de-identification, there is no intention of future re-identification, though it is technically possible [53].

3.3.1 ANONYMISATION

Kleinberg et al. [54] proposed Textwash, an open-source software for automated text anonymisation, that removes personal data while preserving text utility for NLP analysis. Textwash was trained on a dataset of 3,717 articles from the British National Corpus, email bodies, and Wikipedia articles. It was then tested on the IMDB movie reviews dataset [55] to assess utility loss. Potentially sensitive and sensitive information was identified using BERT, fine-tuned for token classification, and then replaced with tags like [FIRSTNAME]. The model achieved a weighted F1 score average of 0.93. On the original dataset, it scored 0.9283, and on the anonymised dataset, RoBERTa scored 0.9204, indicating negligible influence on downstream tasks. A human intruder test showed that anonymity was maintained 74% of the time. While Textwash effectively anonymises data with minimal risk and high utility, the current procedure assumes a uniform ability to be anonymised across documents, for example, equal distribution of personal data.

In contrast, Diaz and Garcia [56] explored the impact of varying values of k-anonymity on the predictive performance of the kNN, RF, Adaptive Boosting, and Gradient Tree Boosting ensemble machine learning models. The classifiers were used to predict whether the income of an individual will exceed \$50,000 per year, using the Adult dataset from the 1994 census database [57]. The features from the census were age, sex, education, relationship, occupation, and native country, with age, occupation, education, and native country anonymised through hierarchies. By applying different levels of anonymity (that is, l-diversity, t-closeness, and δ -disclosure privacy and 5-anonymity) to this dataset, using the ARX software, they found that the ensemble classifier obtained the highest accuracy (0.8352) was achieved with raw data, with slightly reduced accuracy (0.8221) at k=5. This study underscores the delicate balance between anonymisation and model performance. However, this study was performed on a very specific dataset, and thus, its real-world applicability may be limited.

Larbi et al. [58] opposed the idea of a universally superior classifier [56], by conducting an extensive evaluation of seven anonymisation and de-identification techniques on clinical data, testing their downstream performance on five clinical NLP tasks on BERT base uncased, Bio+Clinical BERT and BERT long document classification. The techniques used were de-identification (masking Personal Health Information (PHI) with XXX), masking of numbers (numerical or alphabetical form), shuffling sentences in a text, and a percentage of words are randomly chosen and swapped throughout the document (Random Swap), Synonym Replacement, Clinical Concept Synonym Replacement and Text Aggregation (merging a certain number of shuffled docs into one thus concealing a patient among other patients). They found that text aggregation, which merges shuffled documents, offered the strongest anonymity but resulted in the most significant performance loss. The most significant loss was 36.97%, from an F1-score of 82.51% on non-privacy-enhanced data. Therefore, the researchers stated that the choice of anonymisation technique depends on the balance between privacy and utility needs, indicating that no single technique is universally superior. A limitation of the study is that some of the techniques compared may not be feasibly implemented on a large scale, for example, text aggregation which leads to fewer training examples for downstream processing as data is merged. Furthermore, in reality, longer text documents might negatively impact the performance of standard BERT models, which can only process up to 512 input tokens.

3.3.2 DE-IDENTIFICATION AND PSEUDONYMISATION

A common thread among studies on de-identification, which preserves data utility for downstream tasks, is the focus on healthcare data, specifically Protected Health Information (PHI).

Vakili and Dalianis [94] de-identified a large Swedish clinical corpus from the Swedish Karolinska Hospital by either removing sensitive sentences or replacing sensitive words with realistic surrogates. Their results showed that using de-identified data for domain adaptation of a general Swedish BERT model [59] did not negatively impact classification performance on clinical tasks, with the pseudonymisation approach yielding the best F1-score for multilabel classification (0.736). This study highlights the effectiveness of de-identification in maintaining data utility. However as it was conducted in Swedish it is unclear whether the results will be reproducible in English.

Two years later, the same researchers from [94], partnered with Aron Henriksson [15] to determine the effect of the pseudonymisation of pre-training and fine-tuning data. Two clinical BERT models (one trained on non-pseudonymised data, and the other trained on pseudonymised data) were evaluated on five classification tasks. In eleven of the twenty-four cases, models fine-tuned on non-pseudonymised data performed better than pseudonymised data. Furthermore, there were no instances where using pseudonymised data in the entire machine-learning pipeline, harmed utility. The highest F1-score achieved on the down-stream utility evaluation, was 0.861 on a Clinical Entity NER task. A limitation is that the models were trained on a small dataset with limited scope, therefore, may have difficulties generalising when presented with novel data.

Similarly, Liu et al. [16] developed an end-to-end de-identification framework for discharge summaries. First, the discharge summaries were annotated to identify the personal data, then six NER models were trained on balanced and imbalanced datasets, and finally, the PII was masked. Subsequently, the researchers used a combination of BiLSTM + conditional random fields (CRF) and CNN algorithms to create a set of six ensembles. Their ensemble model achieved strong F1-scores when combined with the stacking SVM method (0.9916) when assessed on the i2b2 dataset [60]. A limitation of automated de-identification systems is the challenge in assessing the safety of sharing de-identified health data and determining the performance reliability of these systems. Without an industry-wide standard, it is difficult to establish consistent benchmarks.

Rastpour and McGregor [61] focused on predicting wait times in mental health care using a proprietary de-identified dataset where both direct and quasi-identifiers were removed. They compared the performance of six machine learning classifiers (LR, RF, weighted kNN, SVM, NN and DT), using features like: referral, triage and appointment dates, priority level (low, medium, and high) designated at triage, status of each appointment (attended, no-show, and cancelled), and possible status changes while waiting or receiving care. It was found that the Random Forest method provided the best performance, by providing the best (minimum) RMSE values for four of the eight clinics and the second-best RMSE for the other clinics. The lowest RMSE attained was 16.49 for the Prompt Care Clinic class. This study underscores the importance of preserving data utility in highly de-identified datasets for accurate predictions. Nevertheless, a limitation of this study is that the dataset was small with 4187 entries, with a lot of variability and did not indicate the resource capacity limitation of the clinics.

In contrast, Baumgartner et al. [62] applied two pseudonymisation techniques to clinical messages from a telehealth system. One technique, P1, pseudonymised names and phone numbers, meanwhile the other, P2, obfuscated proper names, hospital names, and other location identifiers. They then evaluated the impact of these techniques on two classifiers when categorizing the messages into Medical Notes, Organisational Notes (contact initiated by a patient), and Technical Notes (technical equipment and/or issues). One classifier used a complex regular expression rule set developed by Wiesmüller et al. [63] and the other classifier used a document embedding model with predefined keyword lists (Lbl2Vec [64]). They found that simpler classification methods combined with ‘yielding pseudonymisation techniques’, maintained higher sensitivity and specificity. Specifically, P1 achieved an accuracy of 0.84, with reduced specificity (0.62), while P2 reached an accuracy of 0.57 with low specificity (0.23). This study highlights the need for a balance between privacy and utility, as more rigorous pseudonymisation methods led to higher false positive rates and reduced classification performance. Notwithstanding, one person was responsible for all pseudonymisation quality evaluation, thus increasing the risk of bias.

3.3.3 DIFFERENTIAL PRIVACY

Differential privacy is where noise is introduced into a data set while preserving the original statistical properties of the dataset. Differential privacy is usually configured with a privacy parameter. This represents the amount of information which can be leaked by the model

and the amount of random noise which is introduced. Therefore, a privacy parameter of infinity means that there is no privacy guarantee and no differential privacy protection. Mattern et al. [65] explored the training of a generative language model with differential privacy to create synthetic data, which was then used to train classifiers. The researchers used three datasets to create the synthetic training data, which was subsequently used to test the models: the IMDB movie reviews [55] and Amazon Sentiment and Product Category review [66] datasets. They implemented differential privacy by fine-tuning GPT-2 with a privacy engine that allowed them to set target privacy parameters and generate synthetic datasets. Then, a shallow support vector machine (SVM) classifier with TF-IDF encodings and a deep BERT classifier with 110 million parameters, were implemented for classification tasks. The BERT classifier achieved the highest accuracy (0.989) when trained on 3000 synthetic samples that were based on the Amazon dataset's Product Category, when the privacy parameter was eight. On the other hand, the BERT model, which was trained on the real dataset, exhibited an accuracy of 0.966. One significant advantage of this approach is that it allows sharing of sensitive datasets with privacy guarantees while maintaining performance comparable to models trained on real data. However, drawbacks include that the model has demonstrated potential for generating incoherent language and some leakage of training data.

Yue et al. [67] developed a pipeline using local differential privacy to sanitise user data before sending it to a service provider, who then fine-tuned models on this sanitised data. The study extracted semantic similarity between tokens, measured via Euclidean distance between embeddings, and employed the SANTEXT and SANTEXT+ algorithms for text sanitisation. The utility of the datasets was assessed with a BERT classifier. On the SST-2 [68] dataset, the SANTEXT+ approach achieved a maximum accuracy of 0.8516, compared to a 0.9251 accuracy of BERT on unsanitised data. This method maintains privacy while preserving data utility, although there is a noticeable performance drop when compared to unsanitised data.

Two years later, Yue et al. [69] also demonstrated that fine-tuning pre-trained generative language models GPT2, GPT2-Medium, and GPT2-Large enabled the generation of useful synthetic text. They tested this data by performing text classification tasks on the Yelp business review [70] datasets using a RoBERTa base model. The model trained on synthetic data generated with DP-trained GPT2-Large (with task accuracy of 0.6936 and 0.7568 for ratings and categories, respectively) had similar performance to the models directly

trained on the original DP dataset (with task accuracy of 0.7014 and 0.7644 respectively). The approach's main advantage lies in the robust privacy protection it offers. However, a limitation of this approach is that differential privacy disproportionately affects classes based on their sample sizes and may have negatively impacted the accuracy of this experiment.

Tran and Xiong [71] also used transformers to implement DP. They introduced DP-LLMTGen, a method for generating synthetic tabular data using large language models (LLMs) fine-tuned through a two-stage process involving differential privacy. The fine-tuning involved learning data formats and feature distributions with privacy-preserving techniques. The synthetic data generated using Llama-2 performed well on statistical fidelity but faced challenges in downstream machine-learning performance. However, the synthetic data provided by DP-LLMGen, when classified by XGBoost, returned an accuracy of 0.831 on the Adult dataset [57], with an AUC of 0.879. Although the high statistical fidelity of this approach is an advantage, it is very computationally intensive, which may impact its real-world applicability.

Finally, Wang et al. [72] proposed the Differentially Private Recurrent Variational AutoEncoder (DP-RVAE) for generating synthetic text data with high utility while preserving privacy. This model uses a dropout and noise-perturbing mechanism and can be deployed in a federated learning setting. The evaluations on the Tweets Depression Sentiment [73] and IMDB Reviews [55] datasets showed that DP-RVAE, when combined with DistilBERT, achieved a maximum accuracy of 0.7102 with a privacy budget of 15 on IMDB reviews. These results outperformed typical centralised and federated training approaches. While this method demonstrated high utility in federated learning settings, its performance on non-independent and identically distributed (non-IID) datasets remains to be evaluated, which is a noted drawback.

Technique	Year	Study	Dataset/ Context	Approach	Classifier(s) Used	Classifier Performance ¹⁷	Key Findings	Limitations
Anonymisation	2022	Kleinberg et al.	IMDB movie reviews	TextWash - Automated text anonymisation using BERT for token classification.	RoBERTa	0.9204 F1-score (anonymised data) vs 0.9283 (non-anonymised data)	High utility is maintained in anonymised data with minimal impact on downstream tasks.	Assumes uniform ability to be anonymised across documents.
	2023	Diaz and Garcia	Adult dataset (1994 Census)	k-anonymity, l-diversity, t-closeness, δ -disclosure privacy applied using ARX software.	kNN, RF, Adaptive Boosting, Gradient Tree Boosting, Ensemble classifier	0.8352 Accuracy (Ensemble classifier on raw data) vs 0.8221 (Ensemble classifier at k=5)	Accuracy is slightly reduced with higher anonymity, demonstrating a balance between anonymisation and model performance.	Study limited to a specific dataset, possibly limiting real-world applicability.
	2023	Larbi et al.	Clinical data (proprietary)	Evaluated 7 anonymisation techniques: PHI masking, number masking, sentence shuffling, random swap, synonym replacement, clinical concept replacement and text aggregation.	BERT base uncased, Bio+Clinical BERT, BERT long document classification	82.51% F1-score (non-privacy enhanced data); -36.97% performance loss with text aggregation (average of the 3 classifiers)	Text aggregation offered the strongest anonymity but resulted in significant performance loss.	Text aggregation reduces training examples and might not be feasible for large-scale implementation.

¹⁷ Where there are multiple classifiers used in the study, the best performance is documented in this column and the name of the classifier is indicated.

De-identification / Pseudonymisation	2022	Vakili and Dalianis	Swedish clinical corpus	De-identification by removing sensitive sentences or replacing sensitive words with surrogates.	Swedish BERT	0.736 F1-score (pseudonymisation for multilabel classification)	De-identification maintained data utility with no negative impact on clinical task performance.	Results are specific to Swedish, limiting applicability to other languages.
	2024	Vakili et al.	Multiple clinical datasets	Comparison of the effects of pseudonymising pre-training and/or fine-tuning data on downstream utility.	clinical BERT	0.861 F1-score (on a Clinical Entity NER task)	There were no instances where using pseudonymised data in the entire machine-learning pipeline, harmed utility.	The models were trained on a limited set of data and therefore may have difficulties generalising when presented with novel data.
	2022	Liu et al.	Discharge summaries	End-to-end de-identification using NER models and BiLSTM + CRF, CNN algorithms for ensemble model creation.	BiLSTM + CRF, CNN	0.9916 F1-score (BiLSTM+CRF, CNN, with stacking SVM method)	High accuracy in de-identifying data without losing data utility.	Lacks industry-wide standards for benchmarking performance reliability.
	2022	Rastpour and McGregor	Mental health care dataset	De-identified dataset with direct and quasi-identifiers removed, predicted wait times using various classifiers.	LR, RF, weighted kNN, SVM, NN, DT	Lowest RMSE of 16.49 for Prompt Care Clinic category (RF)	Importance of preserving data utility in highly de-identified datasets for accurate predictions emphasised.	Small dataset with high variability; lack of resource capacity limitations for clinics.
	2022	Baumgartner et al.	Telehealth system clinical messages	Two pseudonymisation techniques applied to clinical messages: one pseudonymised names and phone numbers, the other obfuscated	Regular expression rule set, document embedding model (Lbl2Vec)	P1: Accuracy 0.84 (high sensitivity 0.94, low specificity 0.62); P2: Accuracy 0.57 (high sensitivity 0.92, low specificity 0.23)	Trade-off between privacy and utility, with more rigorous pseudonymisation leading to higher false positives.	Evaluation of pseudonymisation quality by a single investigator increases potential bias.

				proper names, etc.				
Differential Privacy	2022	Mattern et al.	IMDB movie reviews, Amazon MultiDomain reviews	Differential privacy in training a generative language model (GPT-2) for synthetic data generation.	SVM (TF-IDF), BERT	0.989 Accuracy (BERT on Amazon Product Reviews)	Allows sharing of sensitive datasets with privacy guarantees, with performance close to models trained on real data.	Potential for generating incoherent language and some data leakage.
	2021	Yue et al.	Stanford Sentiment Treebank	Local differential privacy to sanitise user data using SANTEXT and SANTEXT+ algorithms.	BERT	0.8516 Accuracy (SANTEXT+ on SST-2)	This approach maintains privacy but with a noticeable performance drop compared to unsanitised data.	Performance drops when compared to unsanitised data.
	2023	Yue et al.	Yelp business reviews	Fine-tuning pre-trained GPT2 models for synthetic text generation under differential privacy.	RoBERTa base model	0.7658 Accuracy (trained on synthetic data); 0.7644 (trained on real data) [Classification type: Review Categories]	Performance of models trained on synthetic data is comparable to those trained on original data with DP.	Differential privacy affects classes based on sample sizes, impacting accuracy.
	2024	Tran and Xiong	Adult dataset	DP-LLMGen: Synthetic tabular data generation using LLMs fine-tuned with differential privacy.	XGBoost	Accuracy: 0.831, AUC: 0.879 (when XGBoost is classifying DP-LLMGen synthetic data)	High statistical fidelity achieved, though computationally intensive, impacting real-world applicability.	Computationally intensive, potentially limiting real-world applicability.

	2023	Wang et al.	Tweets Depression Sentiment, IMDB Reviews	DP-RVAE for synthetic text data generation in federated learning settings using DistilBERT.	DistilBERT	Accuracy: 0.7102 (IMDB reviews)	High utility in federated learning settings, outperforming traditional centralised and federated approaches.	Performance on non-IID datasets not evaluated.
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Table 3.3. Table showing a summary of recent privacy-preserving techniques in machine learning (2022-2024) (Source: Author)

4 EU legislation impacting the solution

This section examines key European Union legislations related to cyber incident reporting and the implementation of privacy-preserving techniques such as pseudonymisation.

4.1 LEGAL REQUIREMENTS FOR REPORTING CYBER INCIDENTS

Multiple pieces of legislation across the EU's legal landscape mandate organisations to report cyber incidents. Firstly, there is legislation which targets specific sectors. The NIS2 Directive (Directive (EU 2022/2555)) [74] mandates that organisations in critical sectors report cyber incidents, or else face administrative fines of up to 2% of global annual turnover. Likewise, the European Electronic Communications Code (EECC) Article 40¹⁸ [75], Electronic Identification, Authentication and Trust Services (eIDAS) [76], Articles 10 and 19, and the NIS Directive [77] Articles 14 and 16, also mandate incident reporting for electronic communications, trust services, ID systems, and Essential and Digital services, respectively.

The General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) [13] in Article 33 requires that data breaches, that is, security incidents involving personal data, be reported in 72 hours to the relevant supervisory authorities. Where this is not done, the data controller and/or his/her organisation becomes liable for fines and possible litigation. The GDPR also has an extra-territorial component, which means that third countries (that is, non-EU countries) with whom the EU exchanges data should have similar data protection standards and

Article 2 states verbatim, “Member States shall ensure that providers of public electronic communications networks or of publicly available electronic communications services notify without undue delay the competent authority of a security incident that has had a significant impact on the operation of networks or services.

In order to determine the significance of the impact of a security incident, where available the following parameters shall, in particular, be taken into account:

- (a) the number of users affected by the security incident;
- (b) the duration of the security incident;
- (c) the geographical spread of the area affected by the security incident;
- (d) the extent to which the functioning of the network or service is affected;
- (e) the extent of impact on economic and societal activities.

Where appropriate, the competent authority concerned shall inform the competent authorities in other Member States and ENISA. The competent authority concerned may inform the public or require the providers to do so, where it determines that disclosure of the security incident is in the public interest.”

environments in place. Therefore, a third country which processes EU data and experiences a data breach may face similar punitive measures.

Of note is that the European Union Agency for Cybersecurity (ENISA) also tracks and analyses reported incidents through its Cybersecurity Incident Reporting and Analysis System (CIRAS) platform¹⁹. ENISA was established under the EC Regulation 460/2004 [78] (now repealed) and is one of the pillars of the European Union's collective cyber-defence response.

These legislations may also dictate the type of data which should be included in the cyber incident reports. This information guides the data acquisition phase of this study since the researcher may be able to predict which industries are more likely to have personal data included in their cyber incident reports. Then, these cyber incidents could be used to train the AI model.

4.2 HOW DOES LEGISLATION DEFINE 'PERSONAL DATA'?

According to the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) Article 4, personal data is defined as any information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person. This includes direct identifiers such as a name, or quasi-identifiers such as factors which are specific to the person's physical, social or other types of identity. The inclusion of quasi-identifiers under personal data was demonstrated in the October 2016 *Breyer* case [95], whereby dynamic IP addresses were regarded as personal data. Therefore, any data that can be used either on its own or when combined with other data, to identify a natural person is considered personal data.

Therefore, this study relies on the GDPR to determine the types of data which will be pseudonymised. In turn, this dictates the entity labels which will be used in the Named Entity Recognition module of this study.

4.3 LEGAL DISTINCTION BETWEEN PSEUDONYMISATION AND ANONYMISATION

The process of transforming personal data in such a way that data can no longer be attributed to a specific data subject without the use of additional information is known as

¹⁹One can view this dashboard, documented by legislation type, at the following link: <https://ciras.enisa.europa.eu/ciras-visual>

pseudonymisation, according to GDPR Article 4(5). Therefore, according to the GDPR, pseudonymised data is considered personal data, since it can be re-identified. However, the GDPR also states that with pseudonymisation, the additional information which can be used for re-identification must be stored separately from the pseudonymised data. This means that pseudonymisation is subject to technical and organisational measures with the aim to prevent re-identification or re-attribution.

According to the GDPR, pseudonymised data is still considered to be personal data, and falls within the scope of the GDPR. Therefore, the rights of data subjects, such as the right of access and rectification, will still apply to pseudonymised data [79]. Nevertheless, pseudonymisation is encouraged as a security measure by lawmakers, as it is a means of data minimisation. This is one of the principles outlined in the GDPR indicating that organisations should practise collecting the minimal amount of personal data needed for its processing purposes.

It should be noted that the GDPR does not define anonymisation [80]. However, the preamble to the GDPR infers that anonymisation is irreversibly removing or altering personal data so that a data subject cannot be identified. At this point, the data is not considered personal data and, therefore, falls outside the scope of GDPR. Notwithstanding, with the increase in processing power and computational ability, the standard at which anonymisation is attained may be lowered. This has created tensions, and in 2019, the Irish Data Protection Commission averred that anonymisation is contextual and relative, though the French Data Protection regulator believes that anonymisation is ‘more absolute’ [14]. Furthermore, legislation like Convention 108+ [81], though not directly defining anonymisation, declares that there is a category of anonymised data whereby re-identification would require ‘unreasonable time, effort or resources’ but is possible.

By choosing pseudonymisation as the privacy-preserving approach for this study, the cyber incident reports will be in scope for the GDPR. Therefore, organisations which use the solution developed in this study may need to implement additional technical and organisational measures in how they store the reports, in order to comply with GDPR.

5 Methodology

5.1 OVERVIEW OF THE PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

The methodology for this study can be grouped into four main stages. Stages two to four are visualised in the graphical abstract in Figure 5.1.

Firstly, a literature review was conducted to determine the research gap and the state of the art in Natural Language Processing, Named Entity Recognition and Privacy-enhancing Techniques.

Subsequently, there was the data acquisition phase. The CECILIA-10C-900 dataset from [18] was manually labelled with the categories from the INCIBE Cyber Incident Taxonomy. Then, the dataset was pseudonymised to create: CECILIA-10C-900-MAS, CECILIA-10C-900-TOK, and CECILIA-10C-900-SUB. These datasets correspond to the pseudonymisation techniques of Data **M**asking, Data **T**okenisation and Data **S**ubstitution.

Next, the datasets were pre-processed and encoded. Using this data, eleven AI models were trained to classify a test set of cyber incidents into categories from the INCIBE Cyber Incident Taxonomies. First, the Machine Learning models were trained. Then, to establish a baseline, the following factors were varied: the presence of pre-processing and the presence of minority classes. Once a baseline was established, the transformers were trained under those circumstances.

Finally, the models' performance on pseudonymised data was compared to their performance on non-pseudonymised data, using the following weighted metrics: F1-score, precision and recall.

Figure 5.1. Infographic illustrating the study's proposed methodology (Source: Author)

5.2 THEORETICAL FOUNDATION OF SELECTED MODELS

Firstly, the literature was reviewed to determine the state of the art at the time of review, in the following areas: Named Entity Recognition, Natural Language Processing and Privacy-preserving techniques. The researcher started by using Google Scholar to identify reviews done in each area within the last two years and then supplemented this information with the *paperswithcode.com* database. This database ranks the top-performing AI models on each dataset by accuracy, F1-score, precision and recall.

Across the literature, AI models were evaluated using different datasets, methodologies and benchmarks. Therefore, careful consideration was given to ensuring that the models reviewed were evaluated using similar metrics and tasks, and were trained and/or tested on similar datasets to the ones used in this research. This provided a more balanced and relevant basis for comparison. Subsequently, the best-performing models and studies were documented and then summarised in tables, highlighting their performance scores and applicability to the research context. The summaries and corresponding tables are found in Section 3 State of the art.

The findings of this literature review also informed the selection of the models and techniques for the experimentation phase. The most-commonly used evaluation metrics in the literature reviewed were selected, for ease of comparison. Models that repeatedly performed well in at least two of the three areas reviewed were also included in this study's experimentation phase. Additionally, the privacy-preserving techniques used were selected based on those requiring fewer resources for implementation and maintaining higher downstream utility of the data.

Following this criteria, seven deep-learning transformers were trained and evaluated, alongside four machine-learning classifiers that used two vectorisers. In this section, the theory behind each of these algorithms will be discussed.

5.2.1 MACHINE LEARNING CLASSIFIERS

The Support Vector Machine (SVM) [82] is a supervised learning algorithm. It is commonly used for both classification and regression tasks, where the goal is to find the optimal hyperplane that best separates different classes in the feature space. For linear separability, SVM maximises the margin between the closest data points (support vectors)

of different classes. For non-linear separability, SVM uses kernel functions (like polynomial and radial basis functions) to map data into a space where linear separation is possible. This classifier is particularly effective in high-dimensional space and works well with datasets that have clear margins of separation and are sensitive to kernel choice and regularisation parameters.

On the other hand, Random Forest [83] is an ensemble learning method relying on decision trees. It merges and builds multiple decision trees during training and combines them to achieve accurate and stable prediction. Each tree in the forest is trained on a random subset of the data with replacement (bootstrap sampling), and at each split in the tree, a random subset of features is considered. The final prediction is made by majority voting (for classification) or averaging (for regression) the outputs of all trees. Therefore, this classifier has the advantage of reducing overfitting by averaging multiple trees and is robust to noise and missing values.

The third Machine Learning classifier, XGBoost [84], implements gradient boosting, which is an ensemble technique that sequentially builds models by training new models to correct the errors of previous ones. XGBoost uses a specific loss function and a gradient descent optimisation technique to minimise loss. It also incorporates regularisation to prevent overfitting and includes features like parallel processing, decision tree pruning, and handling missing values natively. Therefore, though this classifier is accurate and efficient, with large datasets and complex relationships it requires careful hyperparameter tuning to avoid overfitting.

Finally, Multinomial Naïve Bayes (MNB) is a probabilistic classification model often used for text data. It operates under Bayes' theorem which relates the likelihood of a class given certain features, to the prior probability of the class and the likelihood of the features. MNB is designed for situations where features are represented as counts or frequencies, such as word counts in documents. The key idea behind MNB is its assumption of feature independence given the class. This simplification allows it to calculate the probability of a document belonging to a class by multiplying the probabilities of individual features. Specifically, it uses the multinomial distribution to model how features (like words) are distributed across different classes. Overall, MNB is effective and efficient, especially for text classification tasks, but it assumes that features are independent, which may not always be the case. Despite this limitation, its simplicity and ability to handle large datasets make it a popular choice for text-based classification problems.

5.2.2 TRANSFORMERS

Firstly, BERT (Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers) [85] is a transformer-based model that reads text bi-directionally. For sequence classification, BERT is fine-tuned with an additional output layer to classify sequences into predefined categories. It uses a combination of masked language modelling and next-sentence prediction during pre-training.

In comparison, RoBERTa (Robustly Optimized BERT Approach) [86] is an optimised version of BERT. It removes the next sentence prediction objective and uses dynamic masking during training. RoBERTa is trained on a larger dataset with longer sequences and larger batch sizes, improving performance on various NLP tasks.

Next, ALBERT (A Lite BERT) [87] is a lighter and faster version of BERT. It reduces the number of parameters by sharing weights across layers and factorising the embedding parameters. ALBERT maintains performance while being more memory-efficient and faster to train.

DistilBERT [88] is another smaller, faster, and cheaper version of BERT. It is trained using knowledge distillation, where a smaller model (the student) learns to mimic a larger model's (the teacher's) behaviour. According to Sanh [88], DistilBERT retains 97% of BERT's performance while being 60% faster and 40% smaller.

BERTweet [89] is another BERT-based model pre-trained on a large corpus of English tweets. It is designed to handle the unique characteristics of Twitter data, such as informal language and abbreviations, making it effective for tasks like sentiment analysis and Named Entity Recognition on social media text.

Finally, two of the models evaluated in this work were trained on the same cybersecurity-related corpus, instead of a general-purpose corpus. These are the SecRoBERTa [90] and SecBERT [91] models. The most significant difference between these models is that one is based on BERT (SecBERT) and the other on RoBERTa (SecRoBERTa). Therefore, SecRoBERTa is pre-trained on a larger corpus, without a Next Sentence Prediction loss. This makes RoBERTa (and by extension, SecRoBERTa) have a more expressive vocabulary than BERT. RoBERTa is also finetuned to better adapt to NLP tasks. Notwithstanding, SecBERT inherits its ability to better capture semantic relationships in phrases from BERT. Therefore, this model may be better suited for tasks which require high contextual understanding.

5.2.3 VECTORISATION

For Machine Learning classifiers, the following encoders were used: Bag of Words (also called Count Vectoriser) and the Term Frequency-Inverse Document Frequency (TF-IDF) vectoriser.

The Bag of Words model is a simple and commonly used method in Natural Language Processing (NLP) to represent text data. *CountVectorizer* is a tool provided by libraries like *scikit-learn* to implement the Bag of Words model. It involves the following steps:

- Tokenisation: Splitting the text into individual words or tokens.
- Vocabulary Creation: Creating a list of all unique words (vocabulary) in the text corpus.
- Vector Representation: Representing each document as a vector of word counts, where each element in the vector corresponds to the frequency of a specific word in the document.

The TF-IDF Vectoriser converts text data into numerical vectors while preserving the context of the text. It operates by carrying out the following steps:

- Term Frequency (TF): This measures how often a word appears in a document. The more frequently a word appears, the higher its term frequency. However, it is normalised to account for the length of the document, ensuring that longer documents do not unfairly boost the frequency of common words.
- Inverse Document Frequency (IDF): This measures how important a word is within the entire corpus of documents. Words that appear frequently across many documents are considered less informative. IDF is calculated by taking the logarithm of the total number of documents, divided by the number of documents containing the word. This reduces the weight of common words.
- TF-IDF Score: The TF-IDF score for a word in a document is computed by multiplying its TF by its IDF. This score reflects both the importance of the word within the document and its relative rarity across the corpus. Words with high TF-IDF scores are both frequent in a specific document and rare across other documents, making them more significant for identifying the document's content.

This method converts text into TF-IDF vectors, helping to capture the essence of the document's content while reducing the influence of common, less informative words.

5.3 DESCRIPTION OF DATASETS

In the State of the art (Section 3), one of the recurring complaints was the lack of a suitable dataset to conduct the experiment. In this body of research, two datasets will be used: CECILIA-10C-900 and CECILIA-10C-900-NER. These will be described in the subsequent sections.

5.3.1 CECILIA-10C-900

Delgado et al. [18] introduced a new cyber incident dataset, CECILIA-10C-900. The name of the dataset was derived from the phrase, **Cy**ber**E**rin**C**idents **c**Lassified **I**NCIBE **t**Axonomy. In this naming convention, 'C' corresponds to the number of categories that the cyber incident dataset includes. This dataset contains 923 cyber incidents, that were collected from the following platforms: European Repository of Cyber Incidents Council on Foreign Relations, Internet Corporation for Assigned Names and Numbers, Names and Numbers Center for Strategic and International Studies, CISSM Cyber Attacks Database and the Open Web Application Security Project (OWASP).

These cyber incidents were then manually labelled by a labelling assistant and cybersecurity expert. Each cyber incident was labelled with a category and subcategory, according to the Spanish National Cybersecurity Institute (INCIBE)'s Cyber Incident Taxonomy The INCIBE Cyber Incident Taxonomy is available in both Spanish [92] and English (refer to Appendix 1). The translation of the taxonomy categories and their corresponding acronyms is seen in Table 5.1. Each cyber incident can be assigned only one category and sub-category label. An example of a cyber incident assigned to each category is seen in Table 5.2.

The CECILIA-10C-900 dataset was chosen for the research because it used the INCIBE Cyber Incident Taxonomy as the basis for its labelling. This taxonomy closely mirrors the European Union Agency for Cybersecurity (ENISA)'s Reference Incident Classification Taxonomy [92]. The ENISA taxonomy is used to standardise cybersecurity incident classification across the European Union. Additionally, the issue of analysing cybersecurity incident reports is particularly pressing in the context of Spain, where the digital economy is rapidly expanding, making the country an increasingly attractive target for cybercriminals [93]. Spanish organisations, particularly small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), often lack the resources necessary to implement sophisticated cybersecurity measures. The

consequences of this gap affect companies' security and financial stability. It also affects the broader national economy and public trust in digital systems. By training the models to perform classification based on this taxonomy, this system will bring far-reaching benefits.

Cyber Incident Category (in Spanish)	Cyber Incident Category (in English)	Acronym
Contenido abusivo	Abusive Content	AC
Obtención de información	Information Gathering	IG
Intento de intrusión	Intrusion Attempt	IA
Contenido dañino	Malicious Code	MC
Intrusión	Intrusion	I
Disponibilidad	Availability	A
Compromiso de la información	Information Content Security	ICS
Fraude	Fraud	F
Vulnerable	Vulnerable	V
Otros	Other	O

Table 5.1. Table showing cyber incident taxonomy categories, from the INCIBE Cyber Incident Taxonomy (Source: Author)

Sample Cyber Incident Description	Category (English)
An unknown actor took control of the Instagram account of the police authority of the German city of Brunswick during the night of 4-5 January 2024. The hijacked account with around 13,000 followers subsequently published suggestive ads, including for a wine seller in Boston. Authorities reclaimed the account later on 5 January.	Abusive Content (AC)
The state-sponsored Iranian hacker group MYSTICDOME (also known as UNC1530, CHRONO KITTEN, STORM-0133) infected four cell phones in Israel with SOLODROID malware, Google's Threat Analysis Group and Mandiant assessed in a 15 February 2023 report.	Malicious Code (MC)
The financially-motivated group 'Scattered Spider' gained access to telecommunication and other business process outsourcing organization's networks in December 2022, through SIM swapping. According to a report by Trellix from 17 August 2023, the threat actors obtained initial access through social engineering techniques directing victims to a credential harvesting site or by directing them to run commercial Remote Monitoring and Management tools giving access to attackers. Scattered Spider used POORTRY and STONESTOP tools to terminate security software and evade detection.	Information Gathering (IG)
The Iranian state-sponsored hacking group 'TA453', aka 'Charming Kitten', gained access to computers of experts in nuclear proliferation policy and Middle Eastern affairs using the GorjolEcho backdoor beginning in mid-May 2023, the US-based IT security firm Proofpoint assessed with high confidence in a technical report on 6 July 2023. In the process, the hackers, linked to the Islamic Revolutionary Guard Corps Intelligence Organization (IRGC-IO), posed as senior researchers and tricked their victims into clicking malicious links. In addition to the GorjolEcho backdoor, the hackers also used the NokNok backdoor to infect Apple macOS operating systems.	Intrusion Attempts (IA)
The Taliban said their phones, email and website had been hacked to spread a false report that the movement's spiritual leader, Mullah Omar, was dead. They identify US intelligence services behind the attack.	Intrusion (I)
North Korea has been hit by a massive cyber attack according to the declaration of a South Korean government official that also added the government of Seoul is investigating on the event denying every responsibility. Russia's ITAR-TASS, which has an office in Pyongyang, reported the events on Wednesday night, all web sites of the country went offline until late Thursday afternoon.	Availability (A)
Unknown actors gained access to the networks of British engineering company Vesuvius, requiring it to temporarily shut down operations, according to legally required declarations by the publicly-traded company of inside information that resulted from its ongoing investigations of the incident.	Other (O)

<p>Mixin Network, a Hong Kong-based cryptocurrency exchange, was the victim of a \$200 million theft from unknown actors on 23 September 2023, making it the largest crypto theft of 2023 at the time of reporting and the 10th largest of all time, according to Reuters. The attack was leveraged through an unnamed cloud service provider for Mixin Network, which allowed the hackers to access the funds. As a result of the breach, Mixin temporarily suspended deposit and withdrawal services while it patched the vulnerabilities that led to the attack.</p>	<p>Information Content Security (ICS)</p>
<p>Thousands of public and private US websites have been compromised to host scammy offers and promotions to children since approximately 2018, according to security researcher Zach Edwards from HUMAN Security, who presented his findings on the still ongoing activity at Black Hat 2023. Among the hijacked websites are those of US government agencies, leading universities, and professional organizations. The purpose of the scam appears to be to trick children into downloading apps, malware, or submitting personal details. According to Edwards, the described activities can be traced back to one advertising company, named CPABuild, who did not respond to inquiries from technology news outlet Wired. In 2020, Italy's Computer Security Incident Response Team (CSIRT) published an alert about compromised domains, including a reference to Zach Edwards</p>	<p>Fraud (F)</p>
<p>According to documents leaked by Edward Snowden, the American NSA and the British Government Communications Headquarters allegedly collected and stored dozens of pieces of data from smartphone apps in a joint initiative called The Mobile Surge until 2007. The main purpose of this was the systematic exchange of ways to obtain information, but information was also tapped, especially from apps that had been around for a while. Publicly, this initiative has been used to gain a better understanding of potential security vulnerabilities that could improve the privacy of citizens' sensitive data in the long term. The UK authority relies on the fact that it would therefore be in compliance with the law. However, it is not known how many users are affected by this action.</p>	<p>Vulnerable (V)</p>

Table 5.2. Table showing a sample of cyber incidents from the CECILIA-10C-900 dataset, assigned to their respective classes from the INCIBE Cyber Incident Taxonomy. (Source: Adapted from Delgado et al. [18], with changes made to the examples and translated categories for better alignment to the current study.)

CECILIA-10C-900 is imbalanced, such that the three smallest categories comprised only 3.30% of the overall dataset, as Figure 5.2 depicts. Furthermore, the dataset contained verbatim duplicated cyber incidents, sometimes having different labels. Therefore, an

additional dataset was created by removing the four least representative categories of the imbalanced dataset: *Intento de Intrusion* (Intrusion Attempts), *Obtención de Información* (Information Gathering), *Contenido Abusivo* (Abusive Content) and *Vulnerable* (same in English) and then removing the duplicated data.

This created two additional datasets: D-CECILIA-10C-900 and D-CECILIA-6C-900. The former dataset is the de-duplicated D-CECILIA-10C-900, without the minority classes removed. Whereas, the latter dataset represented the de-duplicated dataset with the minority classes removed. Section 5.4.4 Pre-processing, describes in greater detail how the de-duplication was done. The statistical features of this dataset are shown in Table 5.3, where it is noted that the de-duplicated datasets appeared to have shorter text lengths.

	CECILIA-10C-900	D-CECILIA-10C-900	D-CECILIA-6C-900
Number of records	923	880	852
Average text length (characters)	821.74	742.10	738.99
Minimum text length (characters)	103	103	103
Maximum text length (characters)	4299	4299	4299

Table 5.3. Table comparing the statistical features of datasets CECILIA-10C-900, D-CECILIA-10C-900 and D-CECILIA-6C-900. (Source: Author)

Figure 5.2. Bar chart comparing dataset distribution between D-CECILIA-10C-900, D-CECILIA-6C-900 and CECILIA-10C-900. (Source: Author)

It is important to note that in Figure 5.2, the number of records in the Availability (*Disponibilidad*) category increased by one cyber incident when the datasets were de-duplicated since an unlabelled record was found in the CECILIA-10C-900 dataset.

Additionally, though the three datasets appear to have the same minimum and maximum cyber incident character lengths, they each had different distributions. Figures 5.3 and 5.4 present histograms of the cyber security incident report lengths in datasets CECILIA-10C-900 and D-CECILIA-10C-900.

Figure 5.3. Histogram showing the distribution of the length of the cyber incident text in CECILIA-10C-900 (characters) (Source: Author)

Figure 5.4. Histogram showing distribution of cyber incident text’s length in the dataset, D-CECILIA-10C-900 (characters) (Source: Author)

5.3.2 CECILIA-10C-900-NER

The CECILIA-10C-900-NER dataset is a Comma-Separated Values (CSV) file created by the Group for Vision and Intelligent Systems (GVIS) Research Group. This dataset is used to perform Named Entity Recognition on the Cyber incidents. CECILIA-10C-900-NER has three columns: the cyber incident text, the category assigned to the cyber incident and the respective NER data. A sample of this NER data is shown in Figure 5.5.

In the NER data column, each entity in a cyber incident is identified and its label stated. Each cyber incident can have one or more entities which correspond to one of eighteen entity labels. These entities represent personal data and possible quasi-identifiers, including name, nationality, location, organisation, events, money, quantities, etc. The

list of all possible entities and their descriptions are seen in Appendix 2. The CSV file also states the entities' positions in the cyber incident text.

In the example shown in Figure 5.5, the entity SB315 (located between characters 38 and 44 of the cyber incident text) is identified as an organisation, and so is given an *Organization* label.

Figure 5.5. Figure showing sample of CECILIA-10C-900-NER file, highlighting the entities and their labels, for a cyber incident (Source: Author)

5.4 PREPARING THE DATASETS

In this section, we will examine how the two datasets were acquired, cleaned and pre-processed in order to be analysed and used as training and testing data for the models.

5.4.1 DATASET ACQUISITION

The CECILIA-10C-900 dataset was obtained from Delgado et al., (with the assistance of the GVIS Research Group) as a CSV file with three columns - the text of the cyber incident, the category and the sub-category with which it was labelled. Additional details about this dataset are documented in Section 5.3.2.

The CECILIA-10C-900-NER dataset was created by the GVIS Research Group, which used Label-Studio, a Named Entity Recognition tool to manually label eighteen categories of entities in the CECILIA-10C-900 dataset. . Additional details about this dataset are also documented in Section 5.3.2.

5.4.2 CLEANING THE DATA

It was observed that though the original CECILIA-10C-900 dataset contained 923 cyber incidents, there were duplicated cyber incidents. A duplicated cyber incident contains the identical wording as another cyber incident.

Cyber incident texts which refer to the same cyber incident are not considered to be duplicates. Duplicates were removed manually using the Microsoft Excel ‘highlight duplicates’ function and then deleted. This was to remove noise in the dataset, since the same cyber incident could be labelled as different categories, and to help reduce the imbalance of the dataset.

5.4.3 NAMED ENTITY RECOGNITION

The cyber incidents in CECILIA-10C-900 contained a mixture of flat, discontinuous and overlapped NER. Using the CECILIA-10C-900-NER dataset, a regular expression was used to extract the entities and their labels from the comma-delimited column. Figure 5.6., provides an example of the entities and labels associated with a sample cyber incident report. In that example, *Norp* represents nationalities and *GPE_Location* represents countries, cities and states. *Quantities* are numbers related to measures of concepts like weight and distance, while *Numbers_C* are numbers which are not *Quantities* nor ordinal numbers. Due to human error and/or biases, in the example shown in Figure 5.6., Artemis Seaford was considered an organisation instead of a person.

Cyber Incident Report and Category	NER Entities	NER Labels
<p>Artemis Seaford, a dual US-Greek Manager from Meta, who lived and worked partly in Greece from 2020 until 2022, was targeted with Predator spyware from September 2021 onwards for at least two months</p> <p>.....</p> <p>The forensic analysis conducted by Citizen Lab revealed an SMS containing a malicious link as the infection vector. Sent five hours after an initial SMS confirmation of a Covid vaccination Seaford had booked in September 2021, the text asked her to click on the link ostensibly to verify the request.</p> <p>Two anonymous sources with "direct knowledge of the case" stated that Seaford had been wiretapped by the Greek national intelligence service EYP in August 2021, a possible indication of how attackers discovered the opening to package the malicious SMS as an appointment confirmation request.</p> <p>(Malicious Code)</p>	<p>'Artemis Seaford', 'US', 'Greek ', 'Meta', 'Greece ',</p> <p>'2020 ', '2022', 'September 2021', 'two months', 'Citizen Lab',</p> <p>'five hours', 'Seaford ', 'September 2021', 'Two ', 'Seaford ',</p> <p>'Greek ', 'Greek national intelligence service ', 'EYP ', 'August 2021']</p>	<p>["Organization", "Norp", "Norp", "Organization", "GPE_Location",</p> <p>"Date", "Date", "Date", "Quantities", ' "Organization",</p> <p>"Quantities", "Organization", "Date", "Numbers_C", "Organization",</p> <p>"Norp", "Organization",</p> <p>"Date", "Date"]</p>

Figure 5.6. Figure showing an example of the entities and labels associated with a sample cyber incident report from CECILIA-10C-900. Labels in red show an example of human labelling error. (Source: Author)

5.4.4 NLP PRE-PROCESSING

The CECILIA-10C-900 dataset underwent six types of pre-processing activities to reduce noise and improve the text's relevance for NLP. These six activities and their purposes are described in Table 5.4. Subsequently, Figure 5.7 shows a portion of a sample cyber incident after pre-processing was completed.

For the CECILIA-10C-900-NER dataset, the NER file's decoding was incorrect therefore special characters, like an accented e, were being reflected incorrectly. These were manually fixed using find and replace in Excel. Other alternatives such as the native Python string decode function were explored unsuccessfully. The comparatively small size of the dataset, paired with the researcher's unfamiliarity with decoding techniques and limited resources made manually correcting the dataset the best option.

It is important to note that there was also pre-processing done that was specific to the Data Substitution task. This is addressed in Section 5.6 Pseudonymisation.

Description	Rationale
Remove special characters	This removes special characters from the text by replacing them with spaces. The regex pattern matches a wide range of symbols, punctuation marks, and other non-alphabetic characters, ensuring that only the textual content remains.
Remove numbers	This matches any sequence of digits and replaces them with a space. This is useful for simplifying the text and focusing on the word content.
Remove single characters	This removes isolated single characters from the text. The regex pattern looks for a single character surrounded by spaces and removes it,
Remove Stopwords	This removes common stopwords (e.g., "and," "the," "is") from the text. The stopwords are fetched using the NLTK library's stopwords function [96], and a regex pattern is created to identify and remove these words from the text, thus reducing noise and improving the text's relevance for NLP tasks.
Implement lemmatisation	Using the <i>WordNet Lemmatizer</i> reduces words to their base or dictionary form (e.g., "better" becomes "good"). Similar to stemming, the text is first tokenised, then each word is lemmatised, and finally, the lemmatised words are joined back into a single string.
Set all text to lowercase	This standardises the text by removing any differences between uppercase and lowercase letters, which is especially useful in NLP tasks to reduce variability in the data.

Table 5.4. Table showing description of pre-processing measures applied to the CECILIA-10C-900 and CECILIA-6C-900 datasets (Source: Author)

Figure 5.7. Figure showing a portion of a sample cyber incident after the pre-processing was completed (Source: Author)

5.5 TRAINING THE MODELS

This sub-section describes how the Machine Learning and Transformer models were trained. First, the CECILIA-10C-900 dataset was divided into a training and test set. Train-test-split was divided such that 30% was test data and 70% to training. The dataset was stratified (using the stratify function) so that there was at least one training sample in each class, due to the imbalance of the dataset. Finally, a seed of 42 was used throughout, to ensure that each classifier was receiving the same test and training data. Models were trained to perform the classification task only using the Category and not the Sub-category field. This is because the dataset was unevenly distributed among the sub-categories.

5.5.1 USING THE MACHINE LEARNING CLASSIFIERS TO CREATE A BASELINE

Next, four machine-learning classifiers were selected and configured using the parameters in Table 5.5. These classifiers were used to determine the baseline performance.

Classifiers	Parameters
Support Vector Machine (SVM)	kernel='linear', class_weight = 'balanced'
Random Forest (RF)	class_weight='balanced', n_estimators=100 (i.e, the number of decision trees) criterion='gini' (quantifies the likelihood that an item in the training dataset is misclassified.)
XGBoost (XGB)	None
Multinomial Naïve Bayes (MNB)	None

Table 5.5. Table showing machine learning classifiers with their respective parameters (Source: Author)

Each classifier was then assessed on two datasets, which could either be pre-processed or not, and two vectorisers. This produced eight possible pipelines for each model:

- D-CECILIA-10C-900 with pre-processing, with BOW vectoriser
- D-CECILIA-10C-900 with pre-processing, with TF-IDF vectoriser
- D-CECILIA-10C-900 without pre-processing, with BOW vectoriser
- D-CECILIA-10C-900 without pre-processing, with TF-IDF vectoriser
- D-CECILIA-6C-900 with pre-processing, with BOW vectoriser
- D-CECILIA-6C-900 with pre-processing, with TF-IDF vectoriser
- D-CECILIA-6C-900 without pre-processing, with BOW vectoriser
- D-CECILIA-6C-900 without pre-processing, with TF-IDF vectoriser

The vectorisers were configured per the parameters in Table 5.6.

Vectoriser	Parameters
Bag of Words (Count)	min_df = 100, ngram_range = (1,2), max_features = 5000
TF-IDF	min_df=5, ngram_range=(1,2), use_idf=True, smooth_idf=True, norm='l2'

Table 5.6. Table showing the vectorisers with their respective parameters (Source: Author)

Subsequently, the dataset and pre-processing status from the pipeline that performed the best were then used to train the transformers.

5.5.2 TRAINING THE VECTORISERS

Seven transformers were trained and evaluated on the D-CECILIA-10C-900 dataset without pre-processing, which showed the best results in the baseline phase of the experiment. All of the models had the training parameters seen in Table 5.7. Additionally, each model used the *AutoTokenizer* function to retrieve the tokenizer associated with the model, for example, BERT used the *BERT Tokenizer*.

Parameters	Value
Number of epochs	3
Training batch size (per device)	8
Evaluation batch size (per device)	8
Warm up steps	500
Weight decay	0.01

Table 5.7. Table showing parameters used to train the transformers (Source: Author)

5.6 PSEUDONYMISATION

Pseudonymisation was chosen as the privacy-enhancing technique for this research, since in the literature, it repeatedly offered the best balance between privacy and data utility. Unlike anonymisation, pseudonymisation allows for deeper investigations of specific cases and other auditing or legal compliance activities where re-identification may be necessary. Furthermore, pseudonymisation is flexible and more granular than other techniques like differential privacy which applies widespread noise to the dataset. Therefore, pseudonymisation can be better customised to varied use cases, such as a company which does not want certain types of data pseudonymised.

Using the entities and labels extracted from the CECILIA-10C-900-NER dataset, each cyber incident was pseudonymised using Data Masking, Data Tokenisation and Data Substitution. The methodologies for each of these techniques are described below. A sample cyber incident from the dataset is shown undergoing the three pseudonymisation techniques in Figure 5.8:

- **Data Masking:** Each entity was identified in the text, and then the entity was replaced with 'xxx'.
- **Data Tokenisation:** Each entity was identified in the text, and then the entity was replaced with the label (for example, *[ORGANIZATION]*, from the CECILIA-10C-900-NER dataset).
- **Data Substitution:** First, for each cyber incident, the dates were removed. This is because if the dates were to be replaced with random dates, this could lead to the pseudonymised data being contradictory. For example, a software data breach could be pseudonymised with a date from before the software was even created. Furthermore, dates are expressed in a variety of formats (January 2020 vs On the 21st of January, 2020) which can make them challenging to process.

Acronyms were also pre-processed. Where an acronym is bracketed after its description, for example, World Health Organisation (WHO), then the acronym will be replaced with the organisation's name. This is known as Acronym Expansion and was used to prevent the substitution algorithm from identifying the organisation and the acronym as different entities. The acronyms were identified by using the Spacy Python library which uses an AI model trained on Scientific data to identify acronyms and their meanings. Any acronyms that the Spacy *AbbreviationDetection* module was unable to detect, were managed by incrementally uploading the dataset to ChatGPT and asking ChatGPT to detect the acronyms. This list of acronyms was then placed in a dictionary, and used to replace their meanings, as before. Finally, using the *Faker* library, fake data was generated for each of the entity types identified in the Named Entity Recognition module of this solution.

An example of this is seen in Figure 5.8, where a cyber incident report underwent Acronym Expansion for the acronym, DIU. Then the cyber incident report was transformed using Data Substitution, where the dates were removed and then the Defence Intelligence Service of Ukraine, was replaced with the Defence Intelligence Service of Coffeychester.

Cyber Incident Report and Category

On 8 February 2024, the **Defence Intelligence Service of Ukraine (DIU)** interfered with the normal functioning of the software used by the Russian armed forces to control drones.

The software is used for modifying commercial off-the-shelf drones from the Chinese manufacturer DJI to meet military purposes. The operation disclosed by **DIU** reportedly cut off drones from the web servers running the software, requiring on-the-ground manual control in close range of the deployment.

Without access to the dedicated software support, Russian drone operators were left without the "friend or foe" identification system and unable to stream video to command posts. Information published by **DIU** indicates the disruption might have been achieved through a denial of TCP connections of the servers.

(Intrusion)

On 8 February 2024, the **Defence Intelligence Service of Ukraine (Defence Intelligence Service of Ukraine)** interfered with the normal functioning of the software used by the Russian armed forces to control drones. The software is used for modifying commercial off-the-shelf drones from the Chinese manufacturer DJI to meet military purposes. The operation disclosed by **Defence Intelligence Service of Ukraine** reportedly cut off drones from the web servers running the software, requiring on-the-ground manual control in close range of the deployment. Without access to the dedicated software support, Russian drone operators were left without the "friend or foe" identification system and unable to stream video to command posts. Information published by **Defence Intelligence Service of Ukraine** indicates the disruption might have been achieved through a denial of TCP connections of the servers.

On , the **Defence Intelligence Service of Coffeychester (Defence Intelligence Service of Coffeychester)** interfered with the normal functioning of the software used by the Urduarmed forces to control drones. The software is used for modifying commercial off-the-shelf drones from the Oromomanufacturer DJI to meet military purposes. The operation disclosed by **Defence Intelligence Service of Coffeychester** reportedly cut off drones from the web servers running the software, requiring on-the-ground manual control in close range of the deployment. Without access to the dedicated software support, Urdudrone operators were left without the "friend or foe" identification system and unable to stream video to command posts. Information published by **Defence Intelligence Service of Coffeychester** indicates the disruption might have been achieved through a denial of TCP connections of the servers.

Figure 5.8. Figure illustrating a sample cyber incident from the CECILIA-10C-900 dataset undergoing the Acronym Expansion followed by Data Substitution. The acronym is bolded. (Source: Author)

| Data Substitution |
|---|--|--|
| <p>xxxx , a dual xxxx -xxxx Manager from xxxx , who lived and worked partly in xxxx from xxxx until xxxx , was targeted with Predator spyware from xxxx onwards for at least xxxx .</p> <p>....</p> <p>The forensic analysis conducted by xxxx revealed an SMS containing a malicious link as the infection vector. Sent xxxx after an initial SMS confirmation of a Covid vaccination xxxx had booked in xxxx , the text asked her to click on the link ostensibly to verify the request.</p> <p>xxxx anonymous sources with "direct knowledge of the case" stated that xxxx had been wiretapped by the xxxx national intelligence service xxxx in xxxx , a possible indication of how attackers discovered the opening to package the malicious SMS as an appointment confirmation request.</p> | <p>["ORGANIZATION"] , a dual ["NORP"] - ["NORP"] Manager from ["ORGANIZATION"] , who lived and worked partly in ["GPE_LOCATION"] from ["DATE"] until ["DATE"] , was targeted with Predator spyware from ["DATE"] onwards for at least ["QUANTITIES"] .</p> <p>...</p> <p>The forensic analysis conducted by ["ORGANIZATION"] revealed an SMS containing a malicious link as the infection vector. Sent ["QUANTITIES"] after an initial SMS confirmation of a Covid vaccination ["ORGANIZATION"] had booked in ["DATE"] , the text asked her to click on the link ostensibly to verify the request.</p> <p>["NUMBERS_C"] anonymous sources with "direct knowledge of the case" stated that ["ORGANIZATION"] had been wiretapped by the ["NORP"] national intelligence service ["DATE"] in ["DATE"] , a possible indication of how attackers discovered the opening to package the malicious SMS as an appointment confirmation request.</p> | <p>Smith-Collins , a dual Hiri Motu - SindhiManager from Thomas, Evans and Wells , who lived and worked partly in Port Bryanfrom until , was targeted with Predator spyware from onwards for at least 6734 .</p> <p>....</p> <p>. The forensic analysis conducted by Nelson-Conway revealed an SMS containing a malicious link as the infection vector . Sent 74436 after an initial SMS confirmation of a Covid vaccination Lee LLChad booked in , the text asked her to click on the link ostensibly to verify the request .</p> <p>4583anonymous sources with " direct knowledge of the case " stated that Lee LLChad had been wiretapped by the Sindh national intelligence service in , a possible indication of how attackers discovered the opening to package the malicious SMS as an appointment confirmation request .</p> |

Figure 5.9. Figure illustrating a sample cyber incident from the CECILIA-10C-900 dataset undergoing the three pseudonymisation techniques (Source: Author)

5.7 EVALUATION OF THE MODELS

Finally, all classifiers were evaluated using the best-performing dataset from the baseline experiment, D-CECILIA-10C-900. The classifiers' performance, when the cyber incidents were pseudonymised with each technique, was compared to when the cyber incidents were not pseudonymised. The metrics used were weighted F1-score, weighted precision and weighted recall. Weighted metrics were used since the dataset was imbalanced, thus adjusting for the differences in class sizes. In section 6.2 Metrics, each of these metrics are described in further detail, including the equation and relevance to the problem.

6 Experimentation and results

In this section, the development environment used for the experiment will be described. This will be followed by a description of the metrics used for the evaluation. This section will conclude by identifying the most suitable machine learning pipeline for classifying pseudonymised cyber incidents and providing the justifications for selecting same.

6.1 DEVELOPMENT ENVIRONMENT

The experiments were done on a Microsoft Windows 11 Pro Lenovo ThinkPad T480 with 24GB RAM, of which 5.35GB remained available during execution. The data handling and the training and evaluation of the models were executed using a T4 GPU on Google Colab Premium, which allowed for longer execution times. The code was written using Python3. Table 5.8 shows the third-party libraries that were downloaded and the purposes for which they were used.

Library	Submodules/Functions	Description
os	None	Interacts with the operating system, handling file paths, environment variables, etc.
re	None	Provides support for regular expressions, used for pattern matching and text manipulation.
numpy	numpy.random.seed	A library for numerical computing, offering support for arrays, matrices, and mathematical functions.
pandas	None	A data manipulation and analysis library, providing data structures like DataFrame and Series.
nltk	tokenize.word_tokenize, corpus.stopwords, WordNetLemmatizer,	Natural Language Toolkit for text processing tasks, such as tokenisation, stopword removal, lemmatisation, and stemming.
sklearn (scikit-learn)	feature_extraction.text.TfidfVectorizer, feature_extraction.text.CountVectorizer, linear_model.LogisticRegression,svm, model_selection.train_test_split,metrics, utils.class_weight, model_selection.cross_val_score, model_selection.learning_curve, metrics.classification_report	A machine learning library providing tools for text vectorisation, classification, model evaluation, and performance metrics.
seaborn	None	A data visualisation library based on Matplotlib, offering attractive and informative statistical graphics.
matplotlib	pyplot as plt, style	A plotting library for creating static, animated, and interactive visualisations.
Spacy	Scispacy	An open-source library which includes an AbbreviationDetector module, useful for identifying and expanding acronyms.
Faker	None	An open-source library for generating fake data, based on a given category, such as nationality, currency, location, and name.
tensorflow	keras keras.callbacks.ModelCheckpoint	An open-source library for deep learning and machine learning, including the Keras API for model building.
gensim	models.word2vec	A library for topic modelling, document indexing, and similarity retrieval, including Word2Vec for word embeddings.
csv	None	Provides functionality to read from and write to CSV files.

Table 5.8. Table showing third-party libraries used with their submodules/functions and descriptions (Source: Author)

6.2 METRICS

The models' performances were evaluated using weighted F1-score, weighted precision, and weighted recall. Below are the formulae for each metric and their interpretations. In the below equation, TP represents a true positive, FP represents a false positive, TN is a true negative and FN is a false negative.

6.2.1 WEIGHTED PRECISION

$$\mathbf{Precision}_{weighted} = \sum_{i=1}^n \cdot w_i \cdot \left(\frac{TP_i}{TP_i + FP_i} \right), \text{ where } w_i \text{ is the weight for class } i \quad (6.1)$$

Precision measures the proportion of correctly classified incidents of a category, out of all incidents that were classified as that category. On other words, this is the accuracy of the model's positive predictions. Weighted Precision considers the precision of each category, weighted by the number of instances (support) in that category. Therefore, majority categories will have a greater influence on the final score. This metric determines how accurate a model's positive predictions are across all categories, taking into account the size of each category.

6.2.2 WEIGHTED RECALL

$$\mathbf{Recall}_{weighted} = \sum_{i=1}^n \cdot w_i \cdot \left(\frac{TP_i}{TP_i + FN_i} \right), \text{ where } w_i \text{ is the weight for class } i \quad (6.2)$$

Recall measures the proportion of correctly classified incidents of a category out of all actual incidents in that category. Weighted Recall considers the recall of each category, weighted by the number of instances in that category thus determining how well each

model is classifying incidents of each category; considering the relative size of each category.

6.2.3 WEIGHTED F1-SCORE

$$F1\ score_{weighted} = \sum_{i=1}^n \cdot w_i \cdot 2 \left(\frac{\frac{TP_i}{TP_i + FP_i} \cdot \frac{TP_i}{TP_i + FN_i}}{\frac{TP_i}{TP_i + FP_i} + \frac{TP_i}{TP_i + FN_i}} \right), \text{ where } w_i \text{ is the weight for class } i$$

(6.3)

The F1-Score is the harmonic mean of precision and recall. A weighted F1-Score takes into account the F1-Score of each category, weighted by the size of that category. Since there may be a trade-off between precision and recall, this metric provides a balanced measure of a model's performance across all categories, with larger categories having more influence on the score.

Notably, accuracy was not one of the evaluation metrics used in this study, though accuracy measures the overall proportion of correct predictions. This is because in an imbalanced dataset (where some categories have significantly more instances than others), a model might achieve high accuracy by simply predicting the majority class most of the time, neglecting the minority classes. Weighted Precision, Recall, and F1-Score provide a more nuanced evaluation, ensuring that the performance in minority categories is appropriately considered. This prevents misleadingly high accuracy scores that ignore poor performance in less frequent categories.

6.3 EXPERIMENTATION RESULTS

This section of the report compares the evaluation of the machine learning classifiers and transformers on the pseudonymised and non-pseudonymised datasets, highlighting the best and worst performances as well as outliers. The report then selects the best model and justifies the characteristics of the model which make it most suitable for the classification task.

6.3.1 MACHINE LEARNING CLASSIFIERS

In this sub-section, the results of the four Machine Learning classifiers: Multinomial Naïve Bayes, Random Forest, Support Vector Machine and XGBoost, when evaluated on two datasets, D-CECILIA-10C-900 and D-CECILIA-6C-900, will be described.

Firstly, the results showed that reducing the number of categories in the dataset did not improve the classifiers' performances. Dataset D-CECILIA-10C-900, without pre-processing, produced the highest average recall, precision and F1-scores. However, some classifiers like XGBoost showed marginal improvements.

Notwithstanding, the XGBoost had the best F1-score across all four datasets examined (0.785), though the Random Forest Classifier showed a similar performance. Of note, is that the Random Forest Classifier performed better on non-pre-processed data. Therefore, its performance declined on both the D-CECILIA-10C-900 and D-CECILIA-6C-900 pre-processed datasets. On the other hand, the Multinomial Naïve Bayes consistently performed the worst, with its lowest F1-score (0.380) obtained in D-CECILIA-10C-900 dataset which was not pre-processed. Additionally, the TF-IDF vectoriser performs better than the Count vectoriser when the data is not pre-processed, in all classifiers except the Multinomial NB. This suggests that TF-IDF vectorisers are better suited for non-pre-processed datasets. Since the models performed the best on the D-CECILIA-10C-900 dataset, this dataset will be used as the baseline on which to compare the performance of the transformers.

		PRE-PROCESSED DATASET			NON-PRE-PROCESSED DATASET		
Classifier	Vectoriser	Weighted Avg Precision	Weighted Avg F1-Score	Weighted Avg Recall	Weighted Avg Precision	Weighted Avg F1-Score	Weighted Avg Recall
MultinomialNB	CountVectorizer	0.644	0.661	0.644	0.770	0.718	0.758
MultinomialNB	TfidfVectorizer	0.733	0.572	0.648	0.752	0.380	0.538
RandomForest Classifier	CountVectorizer	0.676	0.589	0.655	0.802	0.737	0.777
RandomForest Classifier	TfidfVectorizer	0.741	0.724	0.735	<u>0.810</u>	0.742	<u>0.780</u>
SVC	CountVectorizer	0.644	0.615	0.602	0.753	0.650	0.708
SVC	TfidfVectorizer	0.730	0.738	0.742	0.786	0.700	0.746
XGBClassifier	CountVectorizer	0.615	0.659	0.655	0.763	0.760	0.777
XGBClassifier	TfidfVectorizer	<u>0.788</u>	<u>0.747</u>	<u>0.765</u>	0.765	<u>0.785</u>	0.777

Table 6.1. Table comparing the performance of ML Classifiers on D-CECILIA-10C-900, with the Count Vectoriser (Bag of Words) and the TF-IDF Vectoriser, with and without pre-processing (Support = 264) (Source: Author)

		PRE-PROCESSED DATASET			NON-PRE-PROCESSED DATASET		
Classifier	Vectoriser	Weighted Avg Precision	Weighted Avg F1-Score	Weighted Avg Recall	Weighted Avg Precision	Weighted Avg F1-Score	Weighted Avg Recall
MultinomialNB	CountVectorizer	0.585	0.630	0.602	0.612	0.613	0.621
MultinomialNB	TfidfVectorizer	0.661	0.464	0.563	0.718	0.609	0.664
RandomForest Classifier	CountVectorizer	0.654	0.500	0.574	0.629	0.544	0.609
RandomForest Classifier	TfidfVectorizer	<u>0.767</u>	0.684	0.730	0.777	0.715	0.75
SVC	CountVectorizer	0.550	0.542	0.543	0.529	0.528	0.527
SVC	TfidfVectorizer	0.723	0.749	0.742	0.754	0.722	0.758
XGBClassifier	CountVectorizer	0.630	0.635	0.633	0.576	0.572	0.605
XGBClassifier	TfidfVectorizer	0.739	<u>0.784</u>	<u>0.762</u>	<u>0.780</u>	<u>0.739</u>	<u>0.762</u>

Table 6.2. Table comparing the performance of ML Classifiers on D-CECILIA-6C-900, with the Count Vectoriser (Bag of Words) and the TF-IDF Vectoriser, with and without pre-processing (support = 256) (Source: Author)

6.3.2 TRANSFORMERS

In this sub-section, the results of the seven transformers, when evaluated on dataset D-CECILIA-10C-900 will be described.

Among the classifiers, RoBERTa performed the best across all metrics. This classifier achieved the best results in precision (0.74), recall (0.78), and F1-score (0.76). DistilBERT showed the second strongest performance with a precision of 0.70 and a recall of 0.77, resulting in an F1-score of 0.73. SecRoBERTa also performs well, with a precision of 0.71, a recall of 0.74, and an F1-score of 0.70, though it does not outperform RoBERTa which was trained on a general corpus.

In contrast, BERTweet shows the lowest performance across the board, with a precision of 0.65, a recall of 0.70, and an F1-score of 0.64. Overall, RoBERTa delivers the most balanced and highest performance, while BERTweet lags behind the others in precision, recall, and F1-score.

Classifiers	Weighted Avg: Precision	Weighted Avg: F1-score	Weighted Avg: Recall
ALBERT	0.67	0.69	0.74
BERT	0.68	0.69	0.73
BERTweet	0.65	0.64	0.70
DistilBERT	0.70	0.73	0.77
RoBERTa	<u>0.74</u>	<u>0.76</u>	<u>0.78</u>
SecBERT	0.70	0.66	0.71
SecRoBERTa	0.71	0.70	0.74

Table 6.3. Table comparing performance of transformers on D-CECILIA-10C-900. (Support = 264) (Source: Author)

6.3.3 PERFORMANCE ON PSEUDONYMISED DATASETS

In this sub-section, the performance of the machine learning classifiers will be compared to the transformers, on the pseudonymised datasets.

The best-performing transformer was RoBERTa, which achieved the highest F1-scores across the three pseudonymisation techniques; all of which were above 0.75 or 75%. However, RoBERTa performed better on the pseudonymised datasets D-CECILIA-10C-900-MAS (F1-score of 0.81) and D-CECILIA-10C-900-SUB (0.80), than on D-CECILIA-10C-900, the non-pseudonymised dataset (0.76). DistilBERT also demonstrated consistent performance across the pseudonymised and non-pseudonymised datasets. However, unlike RoBERTa, DistilBERT attained its highest F1-score of 0.72 when the dataset was non-pseudonymised. Both DistilBERT and RoBERTa also showed an increased precision on all pseudonymised datasets.

In each of the three pseudonymised datasets, XGBoost with TF-IDF also achieved the highest F1-scores of all the Machine Learning classifiers. Overall, its highest F1-score was 0.83, on D-CECILIA-10C-900-SUB. Like with RoBERTa, XGBoost with TF-IDF performed better on pseudonymised data, then on non-pseudonymised data (0.78). This means that overall, XGBoost outperformed all other Machine Learning classifiers and transformers on pseudonymised data.

This is in contrast to ALBERT which experienced a significant drop in performance when evaluated on each of the pseudonymised datasets, in comparison to the non-pseudonymised

dataset. Furthermore, ALBERT experienced its worst performance, with F1 scores as low as 0.56, on the D-CECILIA-10C-900-SUB dataset. However, Multinomial NB performed consistently worse, on the pseudonymised data with F1-scores of 0.38 for all three pseudonymisation techniques.

It is important to note that the transformers that were pre-trained on a cybersecurity corpus, SecBERT and SecRoBERTa performed the worst on D-CECILIA-10C-900-TOK and the best on D-CECILIA-10C-900-MAS. Notwithstanding, SecBERT still performed better when the data was substituted than when it was non-pseudonymised.

On average, both transformers and machine learning classifiers performed better on the Data Masking dataset than the non-pseudonymised dataset. Furthermore, the average precision and recall was greatest for both classifier types when classifying the D-CECILIA-10C-900-MAS dataset, in comparison to the other pseudonymisation techniques.

Classifier	Vectoriser	Weighted Precision	Avg	Weighted Avg F1-Score	Weighted Avg Recall
MultinomialNB	CountVectorizer	0.770		0.718	0.756
MultinomialNB	TfidfVectorizer	0.750		0.380	0.538
RandomForestClassifier	CountVectorizer	0.789		0.726	0.765
RandomForestClassifier	TfidfVectorizer	<u>0.827</u>		0.763	<u>0.795</u>
SVC	CountVectorizer	0.753		0.650	0.708
SVC	TfidfVectorizer	0.786		0.700	0.746
XGBClassifier	CountVectorizer	0.763		0.760	0.777
XGBClassifier	TfidfVectorizer	0.765		<u>0.785</u>	0.777

Table 6.4. Table comparing the performance of machine learning classifiers on pseudonymised cyber incidents - D-CECILIA-10C-900-MAS (support = 264). (Source: Author)

Classifier	Vectoriser	Weighted Avg Precision	Weighted Avg F1-Score	Weighted Avg Recall
MultinomialNB	CountVectorizer	0.763	0.710	0.750
MultinomialNB	TfidfVectorizer	0.752	0.380	0.538
RandomForestClassifier	CountVectorizer	0.777	0.713	0.754
RandomForestClassifier	TfidfVectorizer	<u>0.796</u>	0.719	0.761
SVC	CountVectorizer	0.726	0.626	0.693
SVC	TfidfVectorizer	0.785	0.704	0.750
XGBClassifier	CountVectorizer	0.776	0.767	<u>0.780</u>
XGBClassifier	TfidfVectorizer	0.744	<u>0.792</u>	0.758

Table 6.5. Table comparing the performance of machine learning classifiers on pseudonymised cyber incidents - D-CECILIA-10C-900-TOK(support = 264) (Source: Author)

Classifier	Vectoriser	Weighted Avg Precision	Weighted Avg F1-Score	Weighted Avg Recall
MultinomialNB	CountVectorizer	0.740	0.678	0.723
MultinomialNB	TfidfVectorizer	0.752	0.380	0.538
RandomForestClassifier	CountVectorizer	0.795	0.722	0.765
RandomForestClassifier	TfidfVectorizer	0.787	0.713	0.758
SVC	CountVectorizer	<u>0.803</u>	0.696	0.746
SVC	TfidfVectorizer	0.762	0.618	0.686
XGBClassifier	CountVectorizer	0.765	0.785	0.784
XGBClassifier	TfidfVectorizer	0.771	<u>0.830</u>	<u>0.807</u>

Table 6.6. Table comparing the performance of machine learning classifiers on pseudonymised cyber incidents - D-CECILIA-10C-900-SUB (support = 264) (Source: Author)

Classifiers	TOKENISATION			MASKING			SUBSTITUTION		
	Weighted Avg: Precision	Weighted Avg: Recall	Weighted Avg: F1-score	Weighted Avg: Precision	Weighted Avg: Recall	Weighted Avg: F1-score	Weighted Avg: Precision	Weighted Avg: Recall	Weighted Avg: F1-score
ALBERT	0.70	0.64	0.61	0.77	0.68	0.61	0.74	0.64	0.56
BERT	0.79	0.73	0.70	0.74	0.72	0.67	0.75	0.72	0.67
BERTweet	0.71	0.68	0.52	0.75	0.68	0.62	0.75	0.71	0.65
DistilBERT	0.79	0.73	0.70	0.79	0.77	0.72	0.78	0.75	0.71
RoBERTa	<u>0.80</u>	<u>0.79</u>	<u>0.76</u>	<u>0.80</u>	<u>0.81</u>	<u>0.81</u>	<u>0.79</u>	<u>0.80</u>	<u>0.80</u>
SecBERT	0.74	0.70	0.67	0.77	0.73	0.70	0.75	0.74	0.74
SecRoBERTa	0.72	0.69	0.65	0.77	0.73	0.70	0.74	0.70	0.66

Table 6.7. Table comparing performance of transformers on D-CECILIA-10C-900 dataset with all three pseudonymisation techniques applied, (Support = 264) (Source: Author)

6.3.4 MODEL SELECTION ANALYSIS

In selecting the optimum pipeline for this solution, there are several factors to be considered. Firstly, the classifier chosen must have strong precision and recall. Having a high weighted precision score means that when the model identifies a cyber incident as Abusive Content, for example, it is very likely to be correct. This is important since several of the classes in the INCIBE Cyber Incident Taxonomy could require urgent incident responses when detected. Therefore, if a cyber incident is classified by a model as Intrusion, but it is actually an Intrusion Attempt, then the incident response team could over-allocate valuable resources to managing that cyber incident. This is avoided by ensuring that the model has high precision, thus prioritising correctly identifying cyber incidents.

On the other hand, a high weighted recall score means that for a class like Vulnerable, most of the actual vulnerabilities will be detected by the model even though some non-vulnerabilities may be incorrectly flagged as a vulnerability. This is important since misclassifying cyber incidents could lead to security breaches. Furthermore, the dataset, like the real world, is imbalanced. Consequently, the model must show high recall for classes that may be comparatively rare, but critical. Additionally, the model must be able to perform equally well or better, on pseudonymised data, as it does on non-pseudonymised data. In this way the solution will not sacrifice downstream data utility, for privacy.

Finally, consideration should be given to the time and effort required to deploy the entire machine learning pipeline. Given the increase in cyber incidents, it is crucial that the model is resource-efficient and able to quickly identify cyber incidents. This need is exacerbated by the European Union's journey to becoming a 'green economy'²⁰.

In summary, the ideal model must demonstrate high recall, especially in minority classes, and consistently high precision scores. Furthermore, it must be able to perform well on pseudonymised and non-pseudonymised data and must be resource-efficient. Based on these criteria, the XGBoost Classifier with TF-IDF with no pre-processing was selected. This pipeline consistently performed well across all pseudonymisation techniques (achieving F1-scores between 0.78 - 0.83), indicating its robustness and adaptability to pseudonymised

²⁰ The European Green Deal prioritises converting the EU into a green or 'resource-efficient' economy. This includes de-coupling the growth of the economy from resource usage and achieving zero greenhouse gases net emission by 2050. More information can be found here [The European Green Deal \(europa.eu\)](https://european-council.europa.eu/media/en/press-communications/infographic/infographic-green-deal-2020-11-14-1)

data. The transformer, RoBERTa also achieved similar performance on pseudonymised data. However, the XGBoost performed the best (out of ML and DL classifiers) with non-pseudonymised data, where it slightly outperformed RoBERTa (F1-score of 0.79 vs 0.76). XGBoost also exhibited a high overall precision of 0.765, exceeding that of RoBERTa, though not achieving the highest overall precision.

Though XGBoost exhibited high recall on some minority classes, such as Availability (*Disponibilidad*) where it achieved a 0.8125 score on the 32 of 264 samples that it was tested on. In spite of this, XGBoost exhibited poor minority class recall. This behaviour was consistent across all models, especially among the three smallest classes, and could be regarded as a flaw in the severely imbalanced dataset.

Finally, since the XGBoost Classifier achieves its best performance without pre-processing, and unlike the transformers does not need to be pre-trained, one may consider it a more efficient use of resources. For these reasons, the XGBoost Classifier is the best performing classifier overall.

7 Discussion of results

In setting the benchmark for this experiment, variables such as vectorisation, pre-processing and removing minority classes from the dataset were explored. The hypothesis was that pre-processing the dataset and making it more balanced through the removal of minority classes, should positively impact the performance of the classifiers since pre-processing reduces noise in the training process and balanced datasets reduce overfitting. Nonetheless, the dataset which yielded the best performance was D-CECILIA-10C-900, without pre-processing.

Furthermore, the best-performing machine learning classifier performed worse when the data was pre-processed, in both datasets (D-CECILIA-6C-900 and D-CECILIA-10C-900). This may mean that the pre-processing techniques used were not suitable for the data. Yokisova et al. [51], who classified vulnerabilities according to a Computer Security Incidents Response Taxonomy, pre-processed their data by only removing stop-words and implementing stemming on the dataset. These researchers achieved a mean accuracy of 0.938 using a Gradient Boost classifier. In contrast, this research pre-processed the CECILIA-10C-900 and CECILIA-6C-900 datasets by removing special characters, single characters, numbers and stop-words. Pre-processing also included using lemmatisation and converting the text to lowercase. Perhaps, this approach may have removed valuable information, and therefore a more minimalistic approach would have been better suited.

On the other hand, the machine learning classifiers performed better on the datasets that did not have the minority classes removed (D-CECILIA-10C-900). This could mean that the machine learning classifiers chosen are resilient to class imbalance. However, in classes where there was only one sample in a class for the test dataset, the machine learning classifiers consistently got that single sample wrong. This shows that despite resilience to class imbalance, the models perform best with more training data.

Finally, the results showed that the best-performing vectoriser was consistently the TF-IDF. This aligns with the algorithm of this vectoriser since TF-IDF incorporates context into the feature vector by including the significance of each vector in its calculations. Whereas, the *CountVectorizer* does not include context and instead counts the frequency with which the words appeared. However, the Multinomial Naïve Bayes algorithm was an outlier, achieving better results with the *CountVectorizer*. This is because the simplistic nature of the Bag of Words algorithm pairs well with the probabilistic algorithm of the MNB.

The RoBERTa transformer consistently outperformed the other transformers in both the classification of the non-pseudonymised and the pseudonymised datasets. This finding is consistent with Delgado et al. [18], whose second-best performing classifier was RoBERTa, achieving an F1-score of 0.8272, using the same taxonomy. Their top-performing classifier, MPNet was not included in the experimentation phase of this body of work.

Of note, RoBERTa achieved its highest F1-score (0.81) on D-CECILIA-10C-900-MAS; exceeding even its F1-score for the classification of non-pseudonymised data. This could be because RoBERTa, unlike ALBERT and BERT, uses dynamic masking during training. That is, RoBERTa is trained on tasks like word prediction by masking different words in each epoch. This may have increased the versatility of the model in comparison to other models which use static masking during training. In static masking, the same word is masked in every epoch. An outlier to this theory is DistilBERT, which performed the second-best, though it used static masking during training. The unpredicted success of DistilBERT could be explored in future work.

It is also important to note that models which were pre-trained on cybersecurity datasets like SecRoBERTa and SecBERT, performed at an average level on the four transformer classification tasks. This shows that general-purpose transformers outperformed transformers trained on cybersecurity corpora. This could be because of dataset drift, whereby the data on which these models were pre-trained no longer represents the current state of cyber incidents. It is recommended that the models are periodically re-trained.

Finally, it was observed that the best-performing transformer, RoBERTa was outperformed by the best-performing classifier XGBoost, and at times RandomForest. What these two ML classifiers have in common is their reliance on decision trees. However, XGBoost uses a strategy which minimises bias and underfitting known as gradient boosting, while Random Forest uses a technique known as bagging, which minimises variance and overfitting. This combination of techniques allows these classifiers to achieve high performance by leveraging the strengths of decision trees while mitigating their weaknesses. The XGBoost achieved its best performance on the D-CECILIA-10C-900-SUB, even outperforming its F1-score on non-pseudonymised data. This type of pseudonymisation might have improved the data quality through reducing noise or irrelevant variations in the model thus making the model more efficient in recognising patterns. In the literature review, one also sees that the Random Forest classifier was among the most successful in NLP classification activities

[5], [8]. Therefore, it may be inferred that decision trees are well adapted to text classification tasks.

However, it is important to note that most models performed their best when classifying the CECILIA-10C-900-MAS dataset. This could be because the masking removed irrelevant data from the text (noise) thus better allowing the models to focus and form trends from the data. On the other hand, the substitution algorithm faced many limitations, which may have impacted the models' abilities to classify that dataset. As the named entities were manually labelled in the text, there were instances where they were incorrectly labelled, such as in Figure 5.6. In that case, the name of an organisation was used to replace the name of a person.

Furthermore, it is possible that context clues that were present in the cyber incident may have been lost during the Data Substitution. An example is where a male's name is replaced with a female's name for a cyber incident in the Abusive Content class, which includes incidents like sexual content. Though, these crimes target both genders, it is possible that the training dataset may not have reflected same. This issue could also have been exacerbated by the removal of dates from D-CECILIA-10C-900-SUB. Vakili et al. [94], resolved this problem by using gender-neutral names in their Data Substitution algorithm. They also replaced locations with other locations in the same country, and replaced the modified dates and ages by increasing/decreasing them by small increments. However, their dataset was limited to Sweden, and therefore this strategy may not be feasible on a global dataset like CECILIA-10C-900.

It is possible that performing pseudonymisation on pre-processed data may have interfered with the Named Entity Recognition portion of this solution. There could have been cases whereby the name of an organisation or person was lemmatised or otherwise pre-processed such that it is no longer been detected as an entity. In this case, that data may remain in the text without being pseudonymised. When this is paired with the human error present in the dataset, this could mean that a few datasets were not completely pseudonymised. Consequently, this explains the consistently better performance of models on non-pre-processed data on the pseudonymised datasets. It is recommended that an ablation study is performed to determine whether pre-processing pseudonymised datasets was negatively impacting the models.

Despite its limitations, this study has revealed that training and evaluation models on pseudonymised data may bolster their classification performance and therefore may be a viable way to classify cyber incidents while preserving privacy.

8 Conclusion

The literature has shown that the reliable and accurate classification of cyber incidents by Artificial Intelligence has been constrained by insufficient training data and the lack of standardisation of cyber incident taxonomies. Furthermore, these models are often trained on cyber incident reports that contain personal data, for example, in spear-phishing incident reports. This not only makes the models susceptible to adversarial attacks which may exfiltrate the personal data, but also discourages cyber victims from reporting cyber incidents. Consequently, there is a need for a privacy-preserving cyber incident classification solution.

This body of research demonstrates that both Machine Learning and Deep Learning classifiers can reliably classify cyber incidents using the Spanish INCIBE Cyber Incident Taxonomy, as applied to the CECILIA-10C-900 [18] dataset. In this study, the XGBoost Classifier performed the best, with an F1-score of 0.785 on this dataset.

This study also introduces three new datasets, D-CECILIA-10C-900-SUB, D-CECILIA-10C-900-MAS and D-CECILIA-10C-900-TOK, which represents the CECILIA-10C-900 dataset pseudonymised using Data Substitution, Data Masking and Data Tokenisation, respectively. The XGBoost model also achieved an F1-score of 0.83 on the D-CECILIA-10C-900-MAS dataset, which was the best performance of any model on that dataset. This shows that the XGBoost model can accurately classify both pseudonymised and non-pseudonymised data, with minimal impact on performance. Therefore, it is feasible to accurately analyse and analyse cyber incidents while safeguarding personal information.

In summary, the results of this research bridge the gap between practical cybersecurity requirements and cutting-edge AI techniques and classifiers. This solution will contribute to greater safety and security in the digital realm.

8.1 LIMITATIONS

There are two main types of limitations: those that are linked directly to the datasets used, and those that arose during experimentation, which are not related to the datasets used. This section explores both, in that order.

8.1.1 DATASET LIMITATIONS

- **Imbalanced Dataset:** The dataset used for training the model was significantly imbalanced, with approximately half of the samples belonging to one class. This imbalance could lead to skewed results, where the model may become biased towards the more frequently occurring classes, compromising its overall classification accuracy.
- **Limited Sample Size:** The relatively small number of samples available for training posed a challenge, particularly since transformer models - which are often employed for such tasks - generally perform better with larger datasets. This limitation may hinder the model's ability to generalise and capture the nuances of different cyber incidents effectively.
- **Labelling Discrepancies:** Both the Cyber Incident (CECILIA-10C-900) and Named Entity Recognition (CECILIA-10C-900-NER) datasets were manually annotated. Therefore, there were mis-classified cyber incidents and instances where an entity in the NER file may be incorrectly identified, or not identified at all. These inconsistencies in labelling could affect the models' ability to accurately identify and classify entities within the cyber incident reports.
- **Issues with Duplicate Data:** During the preprocessing phase, duplicated cyber incidents were removed from the dataset. During this process, there were instances where two identical incidents would have different classifications. When deleting the duplicates, there was no process in place to ensure that the 'less correct' category assignment was deleted, which may result in the retention of incorrectly labelled data and impact the models' performance.
- **Dataset Drift:** The data used may not accurately represent current trends in cyber incidents. This limitation means the model might not be well-equipped to handle emerging or evolving threats that were not adequately covered in the training dataset.

8.1.2 EXPERIMENTAL LIMITATIONS

- **Substitution Discrepancies:** When applying Data Substitution to the dataset, some of the original data's discrepancies in NER labelling were preserved. This means that

the issues with incorrect or inconsistent labelling in the original dataset could still affect the pseudonymised dataset, potentially compromising the accuracy of the model's classification.

- **Coherency Issues with Substitution:** The current approach to handling substitution may introduce coherency issues. Where the transformed data may not consistently align with the original context or meaning, this potentially affects the reliability of the classification. For example, the process of substituting numerical values in the data might have altered the scale or magnitude of certain features. Since transformers are sensitive to such changes, this could lead to distortions in how the model interprets and processes these features.
- **Scalability of Acronym Handling:** The method currently used for managing acronyms within the dataset is not scalable. As the dataset grows or evolves, the existing approach may become increasingly inadequate, necessitating a more robust solution for acronym handling to maintain classification accuracy and efficiency.

9 Future works

Given the limitations discussed in the previous section, the researcher recommends that there be future works carried out. It is recommended that the model is assessed for its adaptability to other taxonomies. Additionally, since all cybersecurity incidents in the dataset were in English, future work could include exploring multilingual datasets where the cyber incidents are reported in several languages. Together, these measures could expand the reach of this solution.

All transformers in this body of work were trained for only three epochs due to computational constraints, however, it is possible that given more time and other resources, the performances of these models could increase provided more training epochs. This presents another avenue for future research.

It is also recommended that alternative Data Substitution algorithms be explored which can provide scalable acronym handling and that can substitute the data without overly manipulating the data's context. This could make the model more efficient and scalable. There is also room for expanding the size of the dataset through automated data scraping, placing a special emphasis on minority classes. Furthermore, it is recommended that a third party review the CECILIA-10C-900-NER dataset for accuracy, as during this experiment there were multiple inaccuracies noted. These inaccuracies may have introduced noise into the dataset and negatively affected the models' performances.

10 References

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²¹ <https://gvis.unileon.es/>

APPENDIX 1: INCIBE cyber incident taxonomy (English)

Source: [Reference-Security-Incident-Taxonomy-Task-Force/working_copy/humanv1.md at master · enisa/Reference-Security-Incident-Taxonomy-Task-Force · GitHub](https://github.com/enisa/Reference-Security-Incident-Taxonomy-Task-Force/blob/master/working_copy/humanv1.md)

CLASSIFICATION (1ST COLUMN)	INCIDENT EXAMPLES (2ND COLUMN)	Description / Examples
Abusive Content	Spam	Or 'Unsolicited Bulk Email', this means that the recipient has not granted verifiable permission for the message to be sent and that the message is sent as part of a larger collection of messages, all having a functionally comparable content. This IOC refers to resources which make up spam infrastructure, for example, harvesters like address verification, URLs in spam emails, etc.
Abusive Content	Harmful Speech	Bullying, harassment or discrimination of somebody, e.g., cyber stalking, racism or threats against one or more individuals.
Abusive Content	(Child) Sexual Exploitation/Sexual/Violent Content	Child Sexual Exploitation (CSE), sexual content, glorification of violence, etc.
Malicious Code	Infected System	System infected with malware, e.g., a PC, smartphone or server infected with a rootkit. Most often this refers to a connection to a sinkholed command and control server.
Malicious Code	C2 Server	Command and control server contacted by malware on infected systems.
Malicious Code	Malware Distribution	URI used for malware distribution, e.g., a download URL included in fake invoice malware spam or exploit kits (on websites).
Malicious Code	Malware Configuration	URI hosting a malware configuration file, e.g., web injects for a banking trojan.
Information Gathering	Scanning	Attacks that send requests to a system to discover weaknesses. This also includes testing processes to gather information on hosts, services and accounts. This includes fingerd, DNS querying, ICMP, SMTP (EXPN, RCPT, etc) port scanning.
Information Gathering	Sniffing	Observing and recording of network traffic (i.e. wiretapping).
Information Gathering	Social Engineering	Gathering information from a human being in a non-technical way (e.g., using lies, tricks, bribes, or threats).
Intrusion Attempts	Exploitation of Known Vulnerabilities	An attempt to compromise a system or to disrupt any service by exploiting vulnerabilities with a standardised identifier such as CVE name (e.g., using a buffer overflow, backdoor, cross site scripting).
Intrusion Attempts	Login Attempts	Multiple brute-force login attempts (including guessing or cracking of passwords). This IOC refers to a resource, which has been observed to perform brute-force attacks over a given application protocol.
Intrusion Attempts	New Attack Signature	An attack using an unknown exploit.

CLASSIFICATION (1ST COLUMN)	INCIDENT EXAMPLES (2ND COLUMN)	Description / Examples
Intrusions	Privileged Account Compromise	Compromise of a system where the attacker has gained administrative privileges.
Intrusions	Unprivileged Account Compromise	Compromise of a system using an unprivileged (user/service) account.
Intrusions	Application Compromise	Compromise of an application by exploiting (un)known software vulnerabilities, e.g., SQL injection.
Intrusions	System Compromise	Compromise of a system, e.g., unauthorised logins or commands. This includes attempts to compromise honeypot systems.
Intrusions	Burglary	Physical intrusion, e.g., into a corporate building or data centre.
Availability	Denial of Service	Denial of Service attack, e.g., sending specially crafted requests to a web application which causes the application to crash or slow down.
Availability	Distributed Denial of Service	Distributed Denial of Service attack, e.g., SYN flood or UDP-based reflection/amplification attacks.
Availability	Misconfiguration	Software misconfiguration resulting in service availability issues, e.g., DNS server with outdated DNSSEC Root Zone KSK.
Availability	Sabotage	Intentional actions maliciously threatening to, attempting to or actually damaging a system or component with the aim of disrupting the availability of a service. These can happen both at logical and physical levels, from malicious firewall rules dropping all traffic, to wire-cutting, bomb threats or arson.
Availability	Outage	An outage caused, for example, by air conditioning failure or natural disaster.
Information Content Security	Unauthorised Access to Information	Unauthorised access to information, e.g., by abusing stolen login credentials for a system or application, intercepting traffic or gaining access to physical documents.
Information Content Security	Unauthorised Modification of Information	Unauthorised modification of information, e.g., by an attacker abusing stolen login credentials for a system or application, or ransomware encrypting data. Also includes defacements.
Information Content Security	Data Loss	Loss of data caused by, for example, hard disk failure or physical theft.
Information Content Security	Leak of Confidential Information	Leaked confidential information, e.g., credentials or personal data.
Fraud	Unauthorised Use of Resources	Using resources for unauthorised purposes including profit-making ventures, e.g., the use of email to participate in illegal profit chain letters or pyramid schemes.
Fraud	Copyright	Offering or installing copies of unlicensed commercial software or other copyright protected materials (also known as Warez).
Fraud	Masquerade	Type of attack in which one entity illegitimately impersonates the identity of another in order to benefit from it.
Fraud	Phishing	Masquerading as another entity in order to persuade the user to reveal private credentials. This IOC most often refers to a URL, which is used to phish user credentials.

CLASSIFICATION (1ST COLUMN)	INCIDENT EXAMPLES (2ND COLUMN)	Description / Examples
Vulnerable	Weak Cryptography	Publicly accessible services offering weak cryptography, e.g., web servers susceptible to POODLE/FREAK attacks.
Vulnerable	DDoS Amplifier	Publicly accessible services that can be abused for conducting DDoS reflection/amplification attacks, e.g., DNS open-resolvers or NTP servers with monlist enabled.
Vulnerable	Potentially Unwanted Accessible Services	Potentially unwanted publicly accessible services, e.g., Telnet, RDP or VNC.
Vulnerable	Information disclosure	Publicly accessible services potentially disclosing sensitive information, e.g., SNMP or Redis.
Vulnerable	Vulnerable System	A system which is vulnerable to certain attacks, e.g., misconfigured client proxy settings (such as WPAD), outdated operating system version, or cross-site scripting vulnerabilities.
Other	Uncategorised	All incidents which don't fit in one of the given categories should be put into this class or the incident is not categorised
Other	Undetermined	The categorisation of the incident is unknown/undetermined.

APPENDIX 2: Entities and Labels in the CECILIA-10C-900-NER dataset

Name: Cyber Incident Dataset, with identified entities - CECILIA-10C-900-NER

This dataset contains 880 cyber incidents from the CECILIA-10C-900 dataset, annotated using Named Entity Recognition to identify entities, their respective labels and the entities' locations in the cyber incident text.

There are 18 possible entity labels:

1. Person: names of persons
2. Norp: nationalities, religious or political groups
3. Facilities: buildings, airports, motorways, bridges, etc
4. GPE_Location: countries, cities, states, etc
5. Location: mountains, rock formations, seas, rivers, etc
6. Organization: organizations, companies, institutions, etc
7. Products: objects, vehicles, meals... we do not include services.
8. Events: sporting events, social events, atmospheric events (hurricanes, blizzards...), wars, battles, etc
9. Law: legal documents
10. Date: absolute dates, relative dates, time periods.
11. Time: any period of time less than one day
12. Art: titles of books, songs or other literary works
13. Money: any monetary value, together with its unit e.g. 500€, \$1000, etc
14. Language: any language
15. Group: groups which are not nationalities, religious groups or political groups, such as hacker groups
16. Quantities: measurements, such as weight, distance, etc
17. Numbers_O: first, second, third, etc
18. Numbers_C: other numbers which are not dates, times, ordinal numbers, or measurements of quantities, etc

(Adapted from Internal Communication of the GVIS Research Group)